

D6.5 - Final Quality Evaluation Report on the RDA TIGER WG Services

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
AIDV	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation
BIDT	Building Immune Digital Twins
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
CoP	Community of Practice
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services (NL)
DSTS_CS-WG	Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations Working Group
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC IM WG	Global Open Research Commons International Model Working Group
I-ADOPT	Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology
IDW25	International Data Week 2025
IG	Interest Group
INSERM	Institut national de la santé et de la recherche médicale
KB	Knowledge Base
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAR	Landscape Analysis Report
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche
maDMPs	Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans

MaLDReTH	Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools
MOMSI	Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration
OfR	Oracle for Research
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
PRO4RS	Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software
QA	Quality Assessment
ReSA	Research Software Alliance
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RFO	Research Funding Organisations
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SC	Selection Committee
TAB	Technical Advisory Board
TRSPs	Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
VP	RDA Virtual Plenary
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report is the final deliverable of the RDA TIGER project's Service Quality work package (WP6). It contains an overview and assessment of the project's approach for measuring the success of its services, how it sought and responded to feedback, an analysis of its key performance indicators, and descriptions of the possible sustainability pathways for the project's results and outputs. Finally, the deliverable concludes with a brief reflection on its overall performance and how the experiences of those who delivered the project could inform future initiatives.

Set against the evaluatory model described in earlier WP6 deliverables and the key performance indicators reiterated below, the project was successful in delivering its services; the service gaps model provided the project partners with a framework by which to invite feedback from service users and allowed the project to respond to feedback with a coordinated, cross-work package approach. Building on the overall sense of goodwill from the RDA community toward the project, the feedback received was overwhelmingly positive. Project-wide and project-specific key performance indicators afforded service providers and work package leads the opportunity to gauge the success of each individual service. These are presented and analysed in detail below.

The feedback provided by service users is also presented in detail below. An analysis of the qualitative and quantitative measures found that, while service users were in the main pleased with the services provided, the project still had aspects of its service offering that needed to be adjusted throughout its lifespan. Feedback was sought and provided on an ongoing basis, meaning the project partners, and WP6 in particular, were required to constantly assess and respond to input from the user community. Alongside this, critical self-evaluation from service providers ensured that the services remained fit for purpose and responsive to the needs of its diverse users.

Alongside the various indicators and feedback that were used to measure the overall quality of the services provided by RDA TIGER, the sustainability of the project's outputs and outcomes are taken as another benchmark by which to judge the project's success. Though the uptake of the results of the project cannot be known at this point, various possible pathways and options have been established during the project lifecycle and are described below.

Finally, some brief recommendations are made for those future projects or initiatives who take on similar or related assignments to that of RDA TIGER. These recommendations are contextualised in the conclusion of this report:

- Ensure that whatever critical or evaluation framework is employed is one that requires input from multiple participants within and/or across different service providers
- Focus on the concision of key performance indicators, success gauges or metrics, ensuring that each allows you to track something specific (i.e., does not need other

information or data to interpret) and worth measuring (i.e., not a “nice to know” statistic)

- Allow space for discussions of service(s) sustainability as early as possible, ideally in parallel to service design and piloting
- Provide multiple methods of feedback to be provided, including ways of recording and responding to conversational and/or anecdotal feedback; communicate to service users the value not only to service providers but to the user community itself of their feedback
- Establish a culture of internal self-evaluation and appraisal of services which allows those delivering the services a say in how these are designed, delivered and adapted.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	6
1. Introduction.....	11
2. Review of methodology.....	11
2.1. Gap analysis.....	12
2.1.1. Knowledge gap.....	13
2.1.2. Policy gap.....	14
2.1.3. Delivery gap.....	15
2.1.4. Communication gap.....	15
2.1.5. Perception gap.....	16
2.1.6. Service quality gap.....	17
2.2. Selection Committee evaluation.....	17
2.2.1. Open Calls for RDA Working Group Support Services.....	18
2.2.2. Cascading Grants and Travel Grants.....	20
2.2.3. Selection Committee composition.....	21
2.3. Landscape analysis methodology.....	22
3. Feedback analysis.....	23
3.1. Feedback gathering.....	23
3.1.1. RDA TIGER Service feedback forms (WG members & co-chairs).....	24
3.1.2. RDA TIGER feedback email address.....	24
3.1.3. RDA TIGER internal feedback survey (provider).....	25
3.1.4. External service quality review.....	25
3.1.5. WG Output quality review.....	25
3.1.6. Qualitative means of feedback collected: Interviews, testimonials, Plenary meetings.....	26
3.1.7. RDA Knowledge Base.....	27
3.2. Feedback results.....	30
4. Key Performance Indicators.....	36
4.1. Project-wide KPIs.....	36
4.2. Communications Service (WP2) KPIs.....	40
4.2.1. Project level Communication KPIs.....	40
4.2.2. Working Group-specific Communication KPIs.....	42
4.2.2.1. KPI update and evolution.....	42
4.2.2.2. Activities carried out and progress report.....	43
4.3. Landscape Analysis Service (WP3) KPIs.....	52
4.4. Outputs Service (WP4) KPIs.....	55
4.4.1. Knowledge Base website metrics.....	55

4.5. Facilitation Service (WP5) KPIs.....	56
5. Sustainability, exploitation and impact beyond project lifetime.....	59
5.1. Sustainability of project results.....	59
5.1.1. Project-based sustainability.....	59
5.1.2. Document-based sustainability.....	60
5.1.3. Sustainability via organisations.....	61
5.1.4. Community sustainability.....	62
5.1.5. Fee-carrying or sponsored sustainability.....	64
5.2. Exploitation of project results.....	64
6. Conclusion.....	67
Annexes.....	70
Annex 1 - RDA TIGER Open Call For Support Services: Selection Committee Evaluation Form.....	70
Annex 2 - RDA new membership before and after the RDA TIGER support started.....	79
Annex 3 - WP2 Communication KPI supplementary materials.....	81

List of figures and tables

Figures

Figure 1. Potential Service Gaps as presented in the deliverable D6.2.....	13
Figure 2. Generic methodology approach used by the Landscape Analysis service.....	23
Figure 3. RDA TIGER feedback form.....	24
Figure 4. RDA TIGER feedback received as part of interviews carried out at IDW2025, and presented at the RDA in Europe Summit in November 2025 in Paris.....	27
Figure 5. Results from the Menti during the April 2025 Knowledge Base Beta Launch.....	30
Figure 6. RDA TIGER services feedback satisfaction.....	31
Figure 7. RDA TIGER Services per Work Package and Working Group stage.....	44
Figure 8. RDA WG member numbers.....	54
Figure 9. Knowledge Base website metrics.....	56
Figure 10. Example of internal WG communications in lieu of ‘bulletins’.....	81
Figure 11. Example WG campaign: RDA TIGER-supported WG Plenary 24 session promotion..	82

Tables

Table 1. RDA TIGER application types and descriptions.....	18
Table 2. RDA TIGER Selection Committee (SC) Members.....	21
Table 3. RDA Knowledge Base events, meetings, and feedback received.....	27
Table 4. Number of feedback responses per RDA TIGER Service.....	30

Table 5. Feedback on aspects of RDA TIGER support services.....	32
Table 6. RDA TIGER project-level KPIs.....	36
Table 7. WP3 Working Group KPIs.....	52
Table 8. Knowledge Base metrics since launch (06/10—11/12, 2025).....	56
Table 9. Facilitation service KPIs.....	57
Table 10. List of published outputs by RDA TIGER-supported WGs.....	63
Table 11. RDA TIGER Key Exploitable Results.....	65

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the final analysis of the quality of the services provided by the RDA TIGER project through its three year lifespan. The project, which began in January 2023, was the first of its kind in that it represented a large-scale, multi-partner endeavour to provide a new suite of services to RDA Working Groups (WGs). These services were to support the work of the WGs, allowing them to produce outputs in the form of RDA-endorsed Recommendations that could be implemented in the EOSC environment. In order to establish these new services and to evaluate and refine them as necessary, the project's Service Quality work package (WP6) was responsible for the overall service quality and for setting up processes to monitor and respond to any feedback received.

The methods of reviewing the services and the model against which to measure any feedback received were set out in D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes¹ and D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions.² Feedback collected on the services was in the main positive and the project largely met its KPIs. This report details the processes by which the delivery of the services was set up and monitored, how feedback on them was collected, how this feedback was interpreted via the critical evaluation model set out in previous deliverables, the role that the project's Selection Committee (SC) played, and finally it presents the potential options for sustaining the services put in place by RDA TIGER beyond the end of the project.

2. Review of methodology

As per the project's Description of Work, WP6 was assigned three main tasks:

- Task 6.1 Demonstrator pilot WG interaction
- Task 6.2 Service Quality Control Coordination
- Task 6.3 RDA TIGER Selection Committee

Following the initial description and launching of the RDA TIGER services with the six Pilot Demonstrator WGs (see D6.3 Report on Pilot Demonstrator Groups³), these WGs were effectively supported by the project as all other WGs were, with the same levels of attention and resources. As such, this section focuses on the methods relating to Tasks 6.2 and 6.3, i.e., the overall model against which feedback was sought and analysed, and how the RDA TIGER Selection Committee was operationalised, including how feedback received at SC meetings was incorporated into the project's work.

¹ Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096659>

² Heikkurinen, M., O'Connor, R., Lehtsalu, L., & Papadopoulou, A. (2024). D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12571122>

³ Rettberg, N. (2023). D6.3 REPORT ON PILOT DEMONSTRATOR GROUPS (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444721>

The service gaps model described below, and the strategies to mitigate them are centred around the Facilitation Service and facilitators themselves. The performance of the Facilitation Service was taken during the project as a reliable indicator of how the in-kind services were performing overall, and as described below, efforts to address any potential gaps were typically undertaken by facilitators. That being said, where necessary, the other three services, Communications, Landscape & Engagement and Outputs Service are invoked.

Finally in this section, it was deemed necessary to include a brief description of the methodology of producing Landscape Analysis Reports, which were produced on request by the Landscape & Engagement Service for any RDA TIGER-supported WGs. The reason this is included here is that specific feedback was sought on these reports from recipients and a description of the method employed to produce these was necessary to put this feedback in context.

2.1. Gap analysis

In this section, the deliverable will consider how the project addressed the five potential gaps described in D6.2⁴ and D6.4,⁵ which are based on the model presented in the “Services Marketing: People, Technology, and Strategy” by Lovelock and Wirtz (Figure 1).⁶ Each of these gaps were crucial in the initial design of the service and in turn in setting the framework for how the project would respond to feedback gathered and incorporate this into quality control.

Before looking in the next section at an analysis of the feedback, this section will present an overview of the five gaps and the steps taken to close these gaps; it will also briefly survey the three additional aspects of service quality mentioned in D6.4 (see section 3.1.7), i.e., goodwill between service providers and its community, the service recovery paradox, and the evolution of satisfaction levels over time (aka the Kano model). Note that the summaries of the gaps provided under each in the boxed text is taken from D6.4.

⁴ Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096659>

⁵ Heikkurinen, M., O'Connor, R., Lehtsalu, L., & Papadopoulou, A. (2024). D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12571122>

⁶ Jochen Wirtz and Christopher Lovelock, Wirtz, J., & Lovelock, C. (2021). Services marketing: People, technology, strategy. World Scientific Publishing Company (2021), ISBN: 978-1944659790

Figure 1. Potential Service Gaps as presented in the deliverable D6.2

2.1.1. Knowledge gap

The knowledge gap is the difference between what management (RDA TIGER, in this case) believes customers expect and what customers actually need and expect

This gap was addressed initially in project design and early stages of delivery, i.e., through the experiences of RDA TIGER project consortium partners and staff with operations of RDA Working Groups and in early discussions with Pilot Demonstrator WGs and their potential co-chairs. However, as noted in D6.4, there was the potential for this gap to grow throughout the project's life in situations where those in receipt of the service were new to RDA, especially those newcomers who assumed WG co-chair positions. There was also a risk of this gap growing in situations where there was an onus on RDA TIGER project partners (specifically, facilitators) to provide the requisite knowledge of how RDA and its WGs operate to WGs with a mixture of co-chairs experienced with RDA and those not.

In these situations, the discretion of facilitators with respect to how much effort was needed to explain how RDA WGs typically operate, making sure all WG co-chairs and members were 'up to speed', then how the RDA TIGER in-kind support services fit into these workflows. Each WG receiving support from the Facilitation Service, the core in-kind service provided by RDA TIGER, was provided with a Service Agreement which was the focus of all initial meetings between RDA TIGER and supported WGs.⁷ The Facilitation Service team also

⁷ See Appendix 1 of RDA TIGER Deliverable 5.1: Rettberg, N., Delipalta, A., & Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D5.1 Definition and handbook of the Facilitation Service (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096642>

produced a RDA TIGER Welcome Pack⁸ for newly-supported RDA Working Groups which aims to ameliorate any impact on WG operations as a result of a knowledge gap between the project and recipients of the services.

2.1.2. Policy gap

The policy gap is the difference between management’s understanding of customers’ expectations and the service standards set for service delivery. Reasons for setting standards below customer expectations are usually related to cost and feasibility considerations.

During the RDA TIGER project lifecycle, there were two main areas where the policy gap between the project’s aims for the service and the recipients’ expectations emerged:

- **Resources:** In some cases through delivery of the service, RDA TIGER facilitators became responsible for activities that typically would be the preserve of WG co-chairs, resulting in the policy gap widening. These activities included the drafting and editing of Statements of Work, setting agendas for regular WG meetings, establishing connections with other related RDA IGs or WGs. Continual efforts were made by facilitators to balance the time and resources devoted to each of their WGs and to ensure that co-chairs would continue to shape direction of the WG; that is, attempting to avoid situations where facilitators become ‘shadow’ co-chairs. In these cases, the policy gap was widening in a positive sense in that facilitators were in some cases contributing efforts above those described in the original service agreement. It is important to note here that evidence of this policy gap widening did not result in any negative formal or conversational feedback; however, it was a topic of discussion among facilitators in Work Package 5 meetings, with discussions focusing on strategies to avoid this gap widening and how to ensure that WG co-chairs in particular fulfilled their responsibilities.
- **Technology:** During the RDA TIGER project, the RDA website migrated to a new platform; this took place over late 2022 to March 2024.⁹ The migration was a difficult process, including a change of web platform providers after the initial transfer because of challenges with the initial provider. During this change and until the new web provider resolved issues with the web platform, RDA group communications were impacted, as the majority of them take place on the platform itself. This created additional support demands for the RDA TIGER team during this period; in particular this resulted in facilitators being required to train WG co-chairs and members in how to use the new website, mitigate any communications issues that arose during periods when website functionality slowed, and where relevant, checking that any material which was hosted on the old website platform was correctly migrated to the new one. Similar to how the project addressed issues to do with resource limitations,

⁸ Papadopoulou, A., Allison, R., Lehtsalu, L., & O'Connor, R. (2025). RDA TIGER Welcome pack - An onboarding guide for RDA Working Groups. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17791908>

⁹ See the update in this ‘The Research Data Alliance (RDA) in 2024: A year to remember’ message to the community: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/the-research-data-alliance-rda-in-2024-a-year-to-remember/>

website updates became a regular topic to be discussed in Work Package 5 meetings, with facilitators sharing mitigation strategies as well as information from WGs' experiences with website performance that needed to be communicated to RDA Secretariat and the web development team.

2.1.3. Delivery gap

The delivery gap is the difference between specified service standards and the actual performance of the service.

RDA TIGER Deliverable 6.4 focuses on potential for delivery gap issues to occur with respect to RDA Plenary events.¹⁰ However, in practice, the main area where a delivery gap manifested was with respect to regular, week-to-week operations of each WG. The main source of issues here, linked to what was referenced above with respect to the policy gap, was to do with potential ambiguity over facilitator and co-chair roles and responsibilities. Though RDA TIGER services were clearly described and defined, in practice the delivery of the Facilitation Service in particular was adapted based on WG needs and co-chairs' preferred ways of operating.

Any potential for a delivery gap to emerge was mitigated through clear communication from facilitators during regular WG meetings and meetings with WG co-chairs about the role of facilitators. One feature of the Facilitation Service which emerged organically over the course of the project was for facilitators to join meetings between WG co-chairs. Most RDA Working and Interest Group co-chairs meet separately from the main group membership meetings to discuss the running of the group and to progress any tasks needing their attention; RDA TIGER facilitators encouraged WG co-chairs to hold these meetings where they were not in place, and used them to articulate where co-chairs needed support and where additional facilitator resource was available.

2.1.4. Communication gap

The difference between what the service provider communicates and what is delivered. The components of this gap are internal and external communications gaps. The internal communication gap can emerge when communications staff operate based on different assumptions of service performance and features than the staff actually delivering the service. The external gap is due to the project overpromising, e.g., in order to increase the visibility of the project and its beneficiaries.

As described in Lovelock and Wirtz and noted in D6.4, issues to do with communication gaps fall into categories of external and internal communications gaps, which were by design limited in the context of the RDA TIGER project and the Communications Service:

¹⁰ Heikkurinen, M., O'Connor, R., Lehtsalu, L., & Papadopoulou, A. (2024). D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12571122>

- **External communications** activities focused on the existing RDA Community (when promoting Open Calls and/or financial support) or on direct, personal communication with new potential co-chairs for WGs.¹¹ Regarding the external communications with the existing RDA community, the messaging focused on describing the support available from RDA TIGER to an audience which was already largely familiar with WG operations and the attendant responsibilities of co-chairs and WG members, meaning that the chances of over- or under-selling the RDA TIGER support was low; with the latter (i.e., new RDA members who were invited to join as co-chairs), the nature of RDA WGs, their typical operations, the requirements of co-chairs, and how RDA TIGER could support them were explained in detail in direct email communications and/or one-to-one meetings, resulting in clear alignment with the service offered and its delivery.
- **Internal communications** gaps similarly were low risk due to the project design as much of the design of communications content for promotion of the services was done by those delivering the services (e.g., promotional webinars for Open Calls, facilitators themselves promoting/communicating the availability of other services and being the main point of contact for these¹²). As with other areas of the project, communications between the different RDA TIGER Work Packages was regular and structured, allowing project partners to get ahead of any potential issues to do with communication gaps.

2.1.5. Perception gap

The perception gap is the difference between what is actually delivered and what the customer feels they have received (due to customers being unable to judge the service quality accurately).

RDA TIGER project services, especially the Facilitation Service, are closely linked to and dependent on progress of the supported WGs (and, at an earlier stage of the project's lifespan, on the provision of the RDA website and WG platforms). As there is such close alignment here with RDA TIGER services (which RDA TIGER partners are responsible for) and the progress of the WG against its stated goals (which WG co-chairs and members are ultimately responsible for), the risk of a gap in perception of the service delivery arises when lack of or slowed progress of the WG is associated with the service provision.

Any potential risks related to this gap were mitigated throughout the RDA TIGER project lifecycle by facilitators being proactive in addressing any issues affecting WG progress and momentum. Example activities that prevented perception gaps developing included WG

¹¹ External communications also included social media promotion; however, the aim of these communications were to reach existing RDA members through social media, or to encourage those who may not be aware of the organisation to become members, with a view to ultimately availing from RDA TIGER service(s) support.

¹² See links to the promotion of RDA TIGER Open Calls, including outreach webinars and presentation materials, on the dedicated RDA website page:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/>

launches or re-launches (where specific meetings or webinars were held to promote new WGs, to recruit new members to existing WGs, or to gain additional input from outside the WG membership on particular topics), rounds of outreach for input and/or new members during the WG's lifespan, and reminders to WG co-chairs and members of pre-approved workplans and timelines from WGs' Statements of Work, and assisting with any WG-related issues requiring conflict resolution. These efforts to ensure that WGs progressed as efficiently and effectively as possible ensured that the chances of issues arising due to Perceptions Gaps were limited.

2.1.6. Service quality gap

The service quality gap is the difference between what customers expect to receive and their perception of the service. It is the aggregate of the above five gaps and will be addressed if all of them are managed in a satisfactory way by the service provider.

The service quality gap describes the overall, cumulative gap comprising the total of any gaps associated with the five previous elements. In order to address this gap, identification of which gap or gaps are causing the overall level of service quality to lower is necessary. As noted in D6.4, the RDA TIGER project benefited from the general goodwill of the RDA community in designing and implementing these services. Another factor that contributed to this overall sense of goodwill was the fact that most of those RDA TIGER project partners contributing to delivering the services were prior members of the RDA community and as such were able to articulate the value of the services from a position of experience. From the perspective of overall service quality and the monitoring of other potential gaps, this initial goodwill coupled with the "insider" knowledge of how the RDA community and its WGs operate meant that any potential gaps in the service delivery could be identified early, thus allowing the project partners to make the necessary adjustments or responses before they developed into issues affecting the overall service quality.

2.2. Selection Committee evaluation

This section describes the implementation of the evaluation procedures used by the Selection Committee under Task 6.1. D1.1: Guidelines for Support Management¹³ requires the SC to evaluate and approve any provision of grants by RDA TIGER. D6.1: Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee¹⁴ in turn sets the rules of procedure for the SC, i.e., how this evaluation process is done in practice.

Project members implemented evaluation procedures to ensure that the criteria for scoring applications were met, as set out in D6.1, and that they adhere to the RDA's governing principles. These evaluation procedures have been improved and adapted where necessary,

¹³ Asmi, A. (2023). D1.1 Guidelines for Support Management (1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099000>

¹⁴ Rettberg, N. (2024). RDA TIGER D6.1 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>

in consultation with SC members, to ensure that they are as accurate and fair as possible. Below, the composition of the SC, and the evaluation procedure as it functioned in the final year of the project are described. This can be considered an update of the D6.1, following feedback and improvements from the SC.

Based on the deliverables listed above and the experiences of the RDA TIGER project, a brief guide, titled ‘10 Things for Running a Selection Committee’¹⁵ was produced, with a target audience of anyone who is tasked with setting up or contributing to the operation of a Selection Committee, whether as part of a Horizon Europe-funded project or other similar initiatives.

2.2.1. Open Calls for RDA Working Group Support Services

The Open Calls refer to public calls for applications for RDA TIGER Support Services. These were done through 4 quarterly call rounds per year throughout the duration of the project, as specified in D6.1 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee¹⁶. The RDA TIGER Support Services consisted of four types of services/applications listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. RDA TIGER application types and descriptions

Application type	Short description
Support Services for the Working Groups provided by the RDA TIGER personnel ¹⁷	Services provided throughout the lifetime of a WG, including Facilitation, communication, landscape analysis, and output support services
Support for hiring external experts for the WG	Hiring externally provided experts for e.g. data collection, interviews, or graphical design
Support for external actions for the WG	Support for purchasing a service by an external provider, e.g. the design of a website
Material support for WG meetings	Support for organising WG meetings, e.g. at a RDA Plenary meeting

The evaluation process followed the five steps outlined below. The associated forms and scoring sheets described here can be found in this [Zenodo record](#).¹⁸

¹⁵ O'Connor, R. (2025). 10 Things for Running a Selection Committee (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18033882>

¹⁶ Rettberg, N. (2024). RDA TIGER D6.1 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218371>

¹⁷ In previous deliverables, also referred to as “in-kind services”

¹⁸ RDA TIGER Support Services: Application forms, evaluation forms, scoring sheets: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734783>

1. **Application:** The RDA TIGER Open Call (non-Cascade Grants, see section 2.2.2 below) was continuously open throughout the project lifetime, with four submission and review deadlines per year. Each call round was communicated on the dedicated RDA TIGER project Open Call page,¹⁹ which also specified eligibility criteria and linked to the latest [application form](#). Details of the Open Calls were made available on this webpage, with any updates on submission dates or adjustments to the application forms made to the page directly (i.e., without creating a new URL for each Open Call). The application form and requirements were available on the website throughout the project; WP6 ensured at least one month's notice where updates to the form were required. This form was updated iteratively throughout the project with input from SC members, to ensure that applications responded to principles of Open Science, EOSC Priorities, and RDA Strategic Plan, and to clarify and improve the usability of the form²⁰. The four types of services outlined in table 1 all use the same form, although different support types use different parts of the form.
2. **Review:** Completed applications were assigned two SC reviewers each by the SC Chair, in consultation with project SC members. Reviewers used an evaluation form²¹ to assess how well the application met various criteria, including relevance to EOSC priorities, eligibility for the call, etc., through both numerical scores and written feedback. The evaluation form underwent several minor revisions with input from the SC to improve its fairness, accuracy, and clarity (see Annex 1 for the latest version of the form). For example, the evaluation form underwent minor updates to be relevant to support types that were launched later in the project (e.g. external action applications). It was also adapted to provide evaluators with more detailed and clear instructions, ensuring that they interpreted the questions the same way. We also added additional options to provide written feedback and clarification for each of the items included in the form.
3. **Scoring:** Scores and comments provided through the evaluation form were passed to an evaluation scoring sheet.²² Here, scores were collated and given scores on different aspects of the application (e.g. the assessed impact of the application on EOSC priorities, its feasibility, and connectivity with other international initiatives), as well as an overall score. These scores were finally transferred to an overview sheet for presentation to SC members during evaluation meetings, where the scores helped assess the eligibility of the application in evaluations. The scoring sheet also underwent a few minor revisions by the SC to ensure that the scores fairly and accurately reflected the merits of the application. These changes mainly concerned

¹⁹ The Open Call page, which now notes that the RDA TIGER Open Calls have all now ended, can be accessed here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/open-call-rda-working-group-facilitation-support/>

²⁰ For the most part these changes concerned updating hyperlinks, clarifying wording, etc. and did not represent substantial changes

²¹ See OC_10_08_25 evaluation form.pdf here: Saldner, S., O'Connor, R., Delipalta, A., Asmi, A., Rettberg, N., Lehtsalu, L., & Heikkurinen, M. (2025). RDA TIGER Support Services: Application forms, evaluation forms, scoring sheets (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734784>

²² Latest version (Open Calls review scores V.5 - example (v.5)) of the scoring sheet, including formulas for calculating scores available in Zenodo record RDA TIGER Support Services: Application forms, evaluation forms, scoring sheets: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734783>

how the scores were presented and collated, e.g. whether multiple scores for certain sections (e.g., EOSC impact) should be calculated as an average score or as the highest of several scores. The formulas used to calculate the scores can be found in the aforementioned spreadsheets, which can be accessed in the footnotes below.

4. **Decision:** The SC met virtually to review applications and decide which applications are accepted. All applications were made available to SC members before the meeting, giving everyone the (optional) chance to read them. The scores provided through step 3 provided one basis for evaluating the merits of the application, and in cases where there were more applications than could be discussed in detail, determined which ones were considered for further discussion. The reviewers of each application briefly outline their impressions, and other SC members were invited to provide theirs. Based on the consensus opinion of SC members, the SC Chair made the decision to either accept, reject, or ask for clarification or adjustment from the applicant.
5. **Communication:** The SC Chair communicated the decision of the SC to each of the applicants, together with feedback provided by reviewers and other SC members.

2.2.2. Cascading Grants and Travel Grants

In addition to the Open Calls, two additional call types were launched. The Cascading Grants²³ (also referred to as Financial Support to Third Parties) allowed researchers, RPOs, and others to apply to receive financial support to adopt the results of RDA WG. Two calls were held in Q1 and Q2 of 2025, both of which were open for two months as per the project's Grant Agreement. Secondly, two Travel Grants were launched in Q2 and Q3, to allow RDA members to apply for funding to attend the RDA 25th Plenary (P25).

Both the Cascading Grant and Travel Grant calls followed a similar evaluation process to that of the Open Calls, however these used different application forms²⁴ and scoring procedures²⁵. D4.1 Final Report On The External And Direct Support Provision And Lessons Learned²⁶ goes into further detail about the aims and objectives of these additional grants.

²³ For more information, refer to the RDA TIGER website:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-2025/>

²⁴ The application form for the first round of Cascade Grants is available on the dedicated webpage on the RDA website here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger-cascade-grants/>; the application form for the second round is available on the dedicated webpage on the RDA website here:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-2025/>.

The application form for the first round of Cascade Grants is available on the dedicated webpage on the RDA website here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/rda-tiger-travel-grants-for-rda-plenary-25/>; the application form for the second round of Cascade Grants is available on the dedicated webpage on the RDA website here:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/rda-tiger-travel-grants-for-rda-plenary-25-2nd-call/>

²⁵ Cascading Grant, and Travel Grant scoring forms:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17734783>

²⁶ Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D1.4: Final report on the external and direct support provision and lessons learned. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17876865>

2.2.3. Selection Committee composition

The original composition of the SC at its launch was outlined in D6.1 (p.8). Here, it was specified that SC membership change was possible on an annual basis, for each of the 4 membership bodies represented, in consultation with other SC members. See table 1 below for an overview of SC membership for each of the membership bodies at the end of the project, based on the similar membership table included in the aforementioned D6.1 outline.

The composition of the SC changed over the course of the project. Members had to be replaced as a result of leaving or changing roles within the project, or because they were unable to meet their SC responsibilities. Additionally, the number of SC members grew from 11 at the beginning of the project, to 14 by its end. The additional members were deemed necessary to meet the high demand for TIGER support services, and assist with the review of the corresponding high number of applications received.

Positions held by RDA TIGER project members (see first section in Table 2 below) were changed to match changes in WP lead positions, as D6.1 specifies that all WP leads shall form part of the SC.²⁷ One RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB) member was replaced, and an additional member added. During the lifetime of the project, individuals were invited to join the Selection Committee due to increases in the amount of applications that the committee needed to review, and due to changes in individuals' ability to contribute time to the committee. When required, the RDA TIGER project team, led by Work Package 6, discussed potential candidates from the RDA community and further afield.

During the course of the project and due to changes in project staff, the chair of the Selection Committee changed from Najla Rettberg (January 2023 - December 2023), to Matti Heikkurinen (April 2024 to October 2024), to Ryan O'Connor (November 2024 to project end).

Table 2. RDA TIGER Selection Committee (SC) Members

RDA TIGER Project Members	
RDA TIGER WP1 (Coordination)	Ari Asmi (RDA AISBL), Alexandra Delipalta (RDA AISBL), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA AISBL)
RDA TIGER WP2 (Communications)	Alexandra Delipalta (RDA AISBL), Anastasia Aritzi (RDA AISBL), Genevieve Halbert (RDA AISBL)
RDA TIGER WP3 (Landscaping)	Laura Molloy (CODATA), Nina Grau (CODATA)
RDA TIGER WP4 (Outputs)	Simon Saldner (DANS)
RDA TIGER WP5 (Facilitation)	Ryan O'Connor (RDA AISBL), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA AISBL)

²⁷ In the case of WP5 & 6, an exception to this rule was made because both WPs were led by the same person, and deputy was substituted instead for WP5

RDA TIGER WP6 (Quality Control)	Najla Rettberg (RDA AISBL), Matti Heikkurinen (formerly RDA AISBL, later CODATA), Ryan O'Connor (RDA AISBL)
Project partner expert members	Carlos Martinez Ortiz (Netherlands eScience Center), Ingrid Dillo (DANS), Simon Hodson (CODATA)
EOSC ASSOCIATION	
Karel Lubyen (President, EOSC Association)	
RDA Technical Advisory Board	
Raphael Cobe (Sao Paulo State University, RDA TAB member)	
Mingfang Wu (ARDC, RDA TAB member)	
Daniel Bangert (TU Delft, RDA TAB member)	
Isabell Perseil (INSERM, RDA TAB member)	
RDA Secretariat	
Connie Clare (RDA Secretariat), Shalini Kurapati (RDA Secretariat), Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Secretary General)	
Other organisations	
Joy Davidson (Digital Curation Centre, University of Glasgow)	

2.3. Landscape analysis methodology

The RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement work package (WP3) provided an on-request service to all WGs receiving in-kind support from RDA TIGER. This service allowed WGs to ask for a report on the general landscape and ecosystem as defined by them in their Statement of Work. The process for requesting a report was for WG co-chairs to contact the service via their RDA TIGER facilitator; the objectives of the report were then defined with the WP3 leader in conjunction with the facilitator. The objectives of these Landscape Analysis Reports depended on the expectations of each WG's request and varied from one request to another. To address this diversity, a generic, broad and concentric methodological approach was developed by crossing diverse ecosystems, from the RDA ecosystem to the grey literature, giving a baseline document for the WGs (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Generic methodology approach used by the Landscape Analysis service.

Before starting the content search within the different ecosystems, appropriate search terms were identified based on each WG’s name and their Statement of Work document (whether draft, in RDA Community Review or having been endorsed by RDA Council). When necessary, WG co-chairs were consulted to validate the selected terms.

As well as generic feedback requests via facilitators to all members of WGs receiving RDA TIGER in-kind support, direct requests for feedback were made to co-chairs of WGs who received Landscape Analysis Reports. Unfortunately, only one response was made to this request; this respondent was ‘Very satisfied’ with the Landscape Analysis Report, noting “as we eventually socialize our recommendations, I think it will be a very important resource for knowing who to contact.”

3. Feedback analysis

In this section, the methods for gathering feedback on RDA TIGER services, an analysis of the feedback received, and a summary of the corrective actions taken is presented. This feedback is then described in the context of the service model gaps detailed above.

3.1. Feedback gathering

Deliverable 6.2 ‘Initial Quality Control Processes’²⁸ outlines a range of suggested means for the RDA TIGER team to collect feedback from the supported WGs, with the aim to continuously evaluate and refine the services. This section describes each method used, provides the rationale for methods that were decided against during the course of the project, and presents the results and analysis of responses collected, also broken down per service.

²⁸ Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096659>

3.1.1. RDA TIGER Service feedback forms (WG members & co-chairs)

As outlined in D6.2, WP6 developed an online feedback form²⁹, based on the questions defined in the same deliverable. This form was distributed at regular intervals to RDA TIGER-supported WG co-chairs and WG members by the Facilitators with the support of WP2 at service initiation, after WG milestones (e.g., completion of Statement of Work, completion of materials prepared by WP2, etc), at the time of active service period end notice issued to WGs in November 2025, and at the completion of the RDA TIGER activities in December 2025. The same form was used for both co-chairs and WG members.

In July 2025 the feedback form was updated to include specific details about the Landscape service (WP3), and an additional campaign was carried out by WP2 to collect responses specifically from Landscape service recipients.

In 2024 and at the time of the RDA Knowledge Base launch and surrounding communication campaign, WP4 and WP6 launched an additional survey³⁰ focused on collecting feedback specifically around this project output in order to gain insight in the quality of information provided during the series of launch events and hands-on workshops, features found to be most useful by the community, suggestions for improvement and further development, etc.

Figure 3. RDA TIGER feedback form

3.1.2. RDA TIGER feedback email address

A general feedback email address was created (rdatiger-feedback@rd-alliance.org) in 2023 and disseminated to the supported WGs, intended to be used as one more means for feedback provision. The email address was monitored regularly by WP2; up until March 2024, when the RDA website migrated to a new provider, no feedback was received in this email address. At the time of the migration to the new RDA website, during which email addresses associated with the previous web provider were terminated, this generic feedback address was evaluated by WP6, and given the lack of any indication of use by the customer base despite frequent distribution, it was decided to discontinue its use and focus on the feedback form as the main means for feedback collection.

²⁹

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfOVdsxSh7Gjvx30lthtDGREQHqTlztJxaSpcOxbEJHIHpDVQ/viewform>

³⁰ <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1luNsJtRTTQHzMCjUj1FAGX7fyArDSX-hjzKKTiZm-o/edit>

3.1.3. RDA TIGER internal feedback survey (provider)

The initial quality control process suggested an internal feedback survey intended for the service providers (i.e., the consortium, and possibly those subcontracted by the coordinator for external expert grants) to self-reflect and support WP6 in service improvement and identifying shortfalls. In practice, it was subsequently decided not to implement an internal feedback form for the following reasons:

- The RDA TIGER consortium consists of a relatively small number of service providers, most playing a role across all WPs and services. The consortium met on a weekly basis at least once but often multiple times a week, where feedback and potential gaps were assessed and discussed in the respective WP meetings (WP1 met weekly, WPs 2 and 5 met fortnightly, WP3 met monthly, WP4 met weekly). In addition to the dedicated WP meetings, WP6 met every 2 weeks to track KPIs and feedback and decide on improvements needed. Finally, WP1 and the coordination team met on a weekly basis to further ensure implementation of actions and address any issues that come up through the feedback mechanisms or in direct correspondence with WGs. As a result, an internal form to be completed ‘by the consortium for the consortium’ was deemed unnecessary, given the very extensive and structured discussions between service providers.
- With regard to service provision by external experts, quality of service was assessed by the WGs themselves (see section 3.1.4).

3.1.4. External service quality review

External experts were engaged and subcontracted by the RDA AISBL, following WG applications as part of the continuously open calls for support. In all cases and as part of the contracting process, the contract stipulated that co-chairs of the WG receiving the support shall conduct the Quality Assessment (QA) of the deliverables produced by the subcontractors. This confirmation of QA having taken place and deliverables meeting the requirements set out in the contract was provided by co-chairs in writing to WP1, after completion of said deliverables and in order for the final payment to be released to the subcontractor.

3.1.5. WG Output quality review

D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes³¹ suggested the creation of an ‘ad-hoc panel of experts’ to evaluate RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs, and create a document on their potential impact, including a qualitative indication of RDA TIGER service impact on the quality of the outputs. This activity was intended to be a quality comparison between historical and outputs created by non-supported WGs, and RDA TIGER-supported WGs, as a means of measuring the impact of the project on RDA outputs. As D6.2 pointed out, such an exercise would have been very subjective, with the usefulness of it ‘to be evaluated internally in WP6 later in the project’.

³¹ Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D6.2 Initial Quality Control Processes (Version 1). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096659>

The creation of an ‘expert panel’ conducting additional quality control on RDA WG outputs after the formal RDA process has concluded (Technical Advisory Board review and RDA Community Review) would have required formal approval by RDA Governance, as it would significantly change RDA process by creating an additional layer of quality assessment for a specific subset of RDA outputs. As a result, project coordination consulted with RDA Governance, including TAB, on the feasibility, usefulness and fairness of introducing such a process. The conclusion from this consultation, also following re-assessment from project coordination, was that such an activity would create an unbalanced, two-tier approach within the RDA where groups selected for RDA TIGER support would be privileged, thereby leading to an imbalance across the whole organisation and group processes. Moreover, such a comparison would inevitably be based on the development of a set of subjective criteria (also retroactively for outputs produced over 10 years ago), thereby minimising the accuracy and credibility of such documentation.

Most importantly the quality and impact of RDA outputs becomes clear based on their adoptability and real-world application; all WG outputs require at least two adopters as part of their endorsement process. RDA TIGER supported this final quality control step by encouraging the community to review the outputs (WP2), by helping co-chairs through the output finalisation process (WP4, WP5), and by reaching out to all adopters on record for the supported WGs to secure adoption stories, and further amplify this potential impact through adoption.

3.1.6. Qualitative means of feedback collected: Interviews, testimonials, Plenary meetings

Feedback was collected in the form of interviews coordinated and filmed by WP2 in person in Brisbane, Australia during International Data Week 2025/RDA Plenary 25 in October 2025. 17 individuals across all RDA TIGER support types (travel grants, cascade grants, and in-kind support recipients) were asked to discuss their key achievements and the added value provided by RDA TIGER. The interview recordings are available on the RDA Association’s [Youtube channel](#) and in a news item on the [RDA website](#). This type of feedback was received in the final two months of the project for communication purposes and is intended as an impact statement with regard to the success of the project, rather than as part of the service improvement process. It is therefore not analysed, and is included here as an additional indicator for the overall service quality.

Figure 4. RDA TIGER feedback received as part of interviews carried out at IDW2025, and presented at the RDA in Europe Summit in November 2025 in Paris.

3.1.7. RDA Knowledge Base

The main source of feedback for the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB) consisted of qualitative feedback gathered during RDA Plenaries, through workshops with users, and in meetings with key stakeholders, mainly with the RDA Secretariat, and TAB. Table 3 below shows a brief overview of these engagements, and the feedback received:

Table 3. RDA Knowledge Base events, meetings, and feedback received

Event/meeting	Description
RDA P21, October 2023	First demonstration of the Knowledge Base concept with real data. The Knowledge Base received positive feedback. Options for establishing groups dedicated to maintaining RDA vocabularies were discussed.
RDA P22, May 2024	First demonstration of an early version of RDA Annotator (then referred to as The Annotation Tool/Platform ³²), together with a round of formal feedback from TIGER users.
RDA Secretariat, September 2024	Work meeting on developing a roadmap towards the launch of the Knowledge Base and its implementation into RDA workflows, website synchronisation, privacy policies, and long-term sustainability.
RDA P23, November 2024	First overview of the full suite of Knowledge Base components as a presentation at an RDA TIGER booth during the event. ³³ Included

³² For details, see D4.2, annex B. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

³³ Slides presented at P23 are available at, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17752536>

	feedback from users and WGs, as well as coordination and planning with RDA Secretariat members about the implementation and sustainability issues.
RDA TAB, February 2025	Demonstration of the Knowledge Base at two TAB sessions, and discussion around potential involvement of the RDA TAB in sustainability solutions.
RDA Secretariat, April 2025	Two-day work meeting around the implementation of the RDA Publisher and integration into RDA Workflows; use and maintenance of vocabularies; role of the RDA in curating Knowledge Base data
Knowledge Base Beta Launch, April 2025 ³⁴	Introducing the beta version of the Knowledge Base to the public. The launch event included a webinar dedicated to demonstrating the Knowledge Base features. The following feedback sessions provided useful input. A Menti poll also provided useful input on what features users were interested in with the Knowledge Base. ³⁵
Hands-on & Feedback sessions, May 2025	Two hands-on and follow-up sessions were organised in early and late May following the Beta Launch. These were particularly directed at RDA WGs, and more interactive. These featured more in-depth demonstration of RDA-KB features, use-cases for RDA WGs, hands-on testing, and opportunities to provide feedback and questions.
Knowledge Base Launch & WG workshop, October 2025 ³⁶	Following further development using the feedback gathered from the Beta Launch events, the official Knowledge Base Launch Sessions on October 6th featured demonstrations of new features, use-cases, and a Q&A session. The launch was followed by a WG workshops that went into further detail on use-cases for WGs, and provided opportunities for WG to discuss their needs and wishes for the Knowledge Base.
RDA P25, November 2025	Presenting the released version of the Knowledge Base, and collecting feedback from users and the RDA Secretariat. Feature requests, including for the inclusion of certain vocabularies were received.
RDA Secretariat work session, December 2025	A half-day work session with the RDA Secretariat to determine how the RDA Publisher will be integrated into the publishing procedures for RDA Groups. A draft workflow was determined, and several

³⁴ Event page: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-tiger-knowledge-base-beta-launch/> (accessed 01-12-2025)

³⁵ Collaborative notes, Menti meter results, and slides from the beta launch session and two follow-up sessions: docs.google.com/document/d/1lrd0aZqBfBXo2ExzNBhqB0hYKZX_czW-UTdF4mOPTyE/

³⁶ A recording of the launch webinar can be found on: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/welcome-to-the-rda-knowledge-base/> (accessed 2025.11.30)

	changes were made to the RDA Publisher relating to UI and use of vocabularies, to further adapt it to the requirements of the RDA Secretariat. Implementation is expected to follow in January 2026.
Knowledge Base Hands-on Sessions, December 2025 ³⁷	Similar to previous events, these sessions (a morning and an afternoon session to accommodate global time zones) were focused on use cases for RDA WGs, and provided another chance for RDA members to get introduced to the RDA-KB, and provide questions and feedback.

Quantitative data consisting of numbers of website visitors, downloads, and other technical metrics relating to Knowledge Base components are continuously collected. However, due to the challenges described in D4.2³⁸ and D4.3³⁹, the Knowledge Base was officially launched quite late in the project, in early October 2025. Quantitative metrics on the Knowledge Base are therefore limited in scope to the first month following its launch, but still provides some encouraging results. See the section 4.4.1 on Key Performance Indicators for more details on this. Useful quantitative feedback was also provided through surveys conducted during the events listed above, as in the figure below:

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-knowledge-hands-on-morning-session/>

³⁸ D4.2 – Performance report on the Output Support Services. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

³⁹ Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2025). RDA TIGER D4.3: Final report on the lessons learned from providing Support Services (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17762711>

Figure 5. Results from the Menti during the April 2025 Knowledge Base Beta Launch

3.2. Feedback results

The project received a total of 36 feedback responses via the feedback form. The breakdown of these by service are displayed below in Table 4. The largest amount of responses was on the Facilitation Service. Most WGs that received in-kind support benefited from support from more than one service; however, it is understandable that this Facilitation Service received the greatest volume of feedback as it was the service with the greatest amount of direct contact with WG members and co-chairs and was in a sense the ‘core’ in-kind service of RDA TIGER.

Table 4. Number of feedback responses per RDA TIGER Service

Service	Number of responses
Communications	4
Facilitation	25
Landscape and Engagement	1

Output Support Services	1
Overall Support	4
RDA TIGER	1

Though there were specific requests to those who received Landscape Analysis Report (LAR) from the Landscape & Engagement Service to provide feedback on this, only one dedicated response was received. It is also worth noting here that one respondent who selected Facilitation in their response to the question, “Which RDA TIGER service would you like to provide feedback for?” mentioned later in their feedback that they also received a LAR, for which they were grateful (“a welcome addition”).

The overwhelming response to the RDA TIGER project and services was positive in tone. As displayed in Figure 6. RDA TIGER services feedback satisfaction below, all but one of the 35 responses received noted that respondents were ‘Satisfied’ or ‘Very Satisfied’ when asked “Overall, how satisfied are you with the RDA TIGER service you have received/are receiving?” The sole neutral response said, “I am about to receive the support, so I cannot answer this question - so far all is very smooth regarding communication.” This is marked by the asterisk in the Figure 6 legend.

Figure 6. RDA TIGER services feedback satisfaction

Regarding the ‘Satisfied**’ response, this was singled out from the other ‘Satisfied’ responses due to the supplementary information the respondent supplied in response to this question; specifically, they noted: “Satisfied with personnel performance within capacity they have had to dedicate to our WG, but dissatisfied with TIGER appetite to use effective communication tools to mitigate gaps in RDA web features.” The response went on to

further express that having access to a shared WG digital calendar would be desirable. However, it was not possible to set this up as it was not possible to compile a separate mailing list for WGs outside the list which was linked to the RDA website’s Posts function (i.e., RDA TIGER could not put together a list of individual WG members’ email addresses as this would risk having WG communications taking place outside the RDA web platform and potentially not being open to new WG *members* and/or to the wider RDA community).

One of the questions posed to respondents focused on the policy gap; “Do you think this service is needed?” The options presented were “Yes, it is valuable for RDA WGs”, “Not so much”, and “I don't know / no opinion”. 34 of the 36 respondents selected “Yes, it is valuable for RDA WGs”. The two remaining responses included one “I don't know / no opinion” and one response via the free text box which said, “I find it extremely helpful and I support this action/ initiative. Being an active member in various community projects, I can verify the importance of this kind of support to drive the project forward.” It is clear from these that any issues to do with the policy gap or designing a service that would fit the community’s needs were small to non-existent. The volume of responses and the share of WGs supported by the project is important to note here too: the RDA TIGER project was supporting the majority of active RDA WGs over the course of its three-year lifespan, indicating that the need for the service was present in the community.

The most important question to which respondents were invited to answer in terms of corrective actions and improvements was, “Please let us know about your experience with RDA TIGER service delivery providing concrete examples, suggestions for improvement and any other feedback you deem relevant.” Responses to this helped the project to address the delivery gap and overall service quality gap.

As noted above, the feedback received for the project was very positive. Some of the aspects of the services which respondents commented favourably are listed in Table 5. below.

Table 5. Feedback on aspects of RDA TIGER support services

Aspect of support services	References in feedback
General organisation, WG operations, WG momentum	15
Meeting organisation	7
Communications materials and collaterals	4
WG outreach, dissemination of activities	4
Internal WG communications	2
Statement of Work production	2

Conflict resolution	2
WG outputs production	1

Some particularly encouraging feedback included:

- A response noting the impact of the WG facilitator and the “huge difference in moving things forward, which otherwise would not happen due to busy schedules of all involved.”
- Another referenced how the support was of benefit from the perspective of someone new to RDA and to co-chairing a WG, with the support providing “an invaluable asset to improving our educational awareness around RDA deliverable process and procedures that could potentially delay progress otherwise.”
- One respondent complimented their WG facilitator, who “has been absolutely awesome” in their support of the WG.
- A respondent put the support into the context of similar Working Group-type enterprises which take place in other organisations: “TIGER support is honestly the best support system I've seen for working groups anywhere.”

Among these supportive comments were two suggestions for areas where the service could be adapted and improved:

- One focused on the scheduling of WG meeting reminders; the respondent commented: “Getting out meeting announcements / invitations in a timely manner feels haphazard.” This feedback was provided in the final six months of the project and the respondent indicated which WG they were referring to in their response; this allowed sufficient time for the issue to be addressed directly by the WG facilitator and also added as an issue to an RDA TIGER All Hands meeting and Work Package 5 - Facilitation Service meeting. The aim here was to remind all facilitators to discuss with their WGs regarding the expected timings of any regular WG communications.
- Regarding potential policy gap issues, identified above regarding the digital tools, one respondent noted that a greater level of cohesion could be achieved across RDA WG operations: “RDA sharing system, GitHub, and google docs and spread sheet; these tools were thought to be good enough but somehow distributed everywhere (maybe because each tool is useful but none of them was perfect, lacking one or two necessary functions; as a result we need to check everything, otherwise easy to forget to access what actually we need to see), and difficult to see everything's list at a glance.” This feedback was provided close to the end of the project, so there are both time constraints as well as technological limitations in how RDA TIGER can respond. However, as RDA Secretariat continues in its dialogue with WGs beyond the end of RDA TIGER, RDA Europe will present this feedback from WGs (and similar, informal conversations) in order to see where improvements could be made in terms of the baseline support and tools provided centrally by RDA to all WGs. This feedback will be provided to RDA Secretariat in a document outlining all lessons learned during the project lifetime and across TIGER services.

There were two questions in the feedback form which relate to the Communications Gap (i.e., questions: “Is the RDA TIGER service in question described clearly (on the RDA website, or via information conveyed to you by the RDA TIGER team)?”, and “Do you have suggestions for improvement to the service description?”). To the former, there were 29 “Yes” responses and two “I don’t know”. Of the free text responses, one, from one of the project’s Pilot Demonstrator WGs, noted that at the outset of the service, project partners were making efforts to translate from how the service was initially described to implementing it practically (“We were one of the first groups to receive TIGER support. Some detail had still to be worked out at the start of the programme.”), while another WG in a similar position noted that it would be working with those delivering the services, in this case the facilitator, on how the support can be implemented (“Because this is new, there is still much to work out, and we do well with identifying opportunities for support as they come available.”). As mentioned previously with regards to the communication gap, efforts made to minimise any potential issues here at the project design stage were successful.

The question “Does the service you received/are receiving accurately reflect the description?”, related to both the communication and delivery gaps. Again, the vast majority of responses were in the affirmative (25 responded “Yes”). There were four “I don’t know” responses, indicative of these respondents’ previous answers relating to the two questions discussed in the previous paragraph. Of the other free text responses here, the sentiment was generally positive; for example: “[the service was] described via the TIGER member telling the WG what they can help with; in this regard, their work matched their described work! :)”, “what I know from memory, yes though we received more than what was described”, and “We also received support in the form of a landscape analysis. This was a welcome addition.” Again, the project partners' efforts to address any potential issues with communication and delivery gaps were successful.

Finally, respondents were invited to contribute some general observations on their experiences of the support provided and suggestions for potential improvements: “Do you have any other general comments or suggestions for improvement of the RDA TIGER services?” There were a few recurring suggestions here, some of which were taken on board by the project and some of which will form the basis of future discussions between RDA Europe and RDA Secretariat on how to embed the experiences and lessons from the project in future RDA WG support processes and workflows.

There were a number of comments in response to the question above relating to general project communications and website visibility. One respondent suggested making the RDA TIGER project space more visible on the RDA website, with another reflecting that the inclusion of success stories would be useful to showcase the services. The former feedback was responded to respectively by making the project space directly accessible from the RDA landing page menu (under the ‘What we do’ heading), the latter by creating communication campaigns around the Grantees, a dedicated RDA TIGER Impact webpage, and showcasing achievements consistently in events where the project is presented.

Related to this, there were further suggestions to improve overall website performance (something that impacted all RDA WG operations in the period March to August 2024 due to issues with the new website platform) and enhance the communications tools made available on the website. Both of these, while key to the operations of all WGs, were largely outside the control of the RDA TIGER team; however, part of the role that developed through the project, especially during the period where website functionality was most acutely affected, was to communicate RDA WG co-chairs' and members' concerns to RDA Secretariat and the website development team, and in turn to relay any updates outside those regular update given to the wider RDA community by RDA Secretariat.⁴⁰

There were two responses which referenced the availability of services and eligibility criteria. On the former, there was a comment that in general it was difficult to tell which of the services was available to WGs. This was addressed in discussions within Work Package 5 to ensure that WG facilitators made their WGs aware that they could avail of all in-kind services, and also through the creation of supplementary online resources describing each service⁴¹ as well as communication campaigns explaining each service⁴². For the latter, there was a request to present the eligibility criteria for applying for travel grants to attend IDW25 more clearly; this was responded to mainly via facilitators informing RDA TIGER-supported WGs of the second round of travel grants and making clear to members the criteria for eligibility, particularly in relation to countries of residence.

There were four references in the responses to this question regarding the possibility of increasing the number of WGs supported by the RDA TIGER project and extending services to Interest Groups (IGs) and Communities of Practice (CoPs). In relation to the latter point, IGs and CoPs were outside the scope of the RDA TIGER project; this was decided at proposal stage as WGs due to their workflows, clear deliverables, scope and 18 month lifespan which allowed for the testing and operationalisation of the support services within the constraints of the project. In terms of supporting more WGs, the number of supported WGs was determined based on how many applications were received in each call, and the results of the SC review process. Rejected applications were always provided with feedback and the necessary input to facilitate their resubmission. All RDA WGs were inherently eligible to receive support following an application and assessment by the SC; due to the process set out in the project's Description of Work for selecting Working Groups which aligned with certain criteria, and the related requirement for an application in order to be considered for support provision, it was not possible to automatically extend RDA TIGER services to all RDA WGs.

⁴⁰ This communications channel was in the form of fortnightly meetings between the RDA Secretariat and RDA Europe, the RDA TIGER project coordinators.

⁴¹ See more detailed description of services here:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/rda-tiger-services/>

⁴² Example service spotlight communication campaign across channels to address providing clarity regarding the availability of different support services:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/rda-tiger-service-spotlight-facilitation/>,

https://mastodon.social/@RDA_Association/110972410697847706

4. Key Performance Indicators

This section looks at the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set out at the outset and tracked throughout the lifespan of the project. There were project-wide and work package-specific KPIs set; this section is divided in sub-sections to reflect how each set of KPIs were monitored separately for each service and how they fed into any quality control actions where relevant.

In general, the project’s performance against its KPIs was strong, both on a project-wide level and from the perspective of individual work packages. In the project design, a hierarchy of KPIs was not established. However, there are several KPIs worth highlighting which are indicative of the overall achievements of the project:

- The overall percentage of positive feedback on the service was **96.1%** (exceeding the target KPI of 95%)
- There were 15 presentations of RDA TIGER at third-party (i.e., non-RDA events) during the project lifetime (exceeding the target of 5)
- The Facilitation Service supported **20** RDA WGs (no target set for this KPI)
- Across virtual (RDA Virtual Plenaries and public WG meetings) and physical meetings (i.e., at RDA in-person Plenary meetings) the Facilitation Service helped to organise **67** events (no target set for this KPI)
- The Landscape & Engagement service contributed to **219** new members joining RDA and RDA TIGER WGs (exceeding the target of 50).

These are explained in more detail in their respective sections below.

4.1. Project-wide KPIs

Project-wide KPIs were tracked by WP6. The status of these KPIs are displayed in Table 6. below, with further explanation of the progress in the paragraphs below. In order to display these more clearly, the ‘External service provision has been successful’ KPIs have been split into four separate KPIs (they were listed as one, with four separate targets, in D6.4).

Table 6. RDA TIGER project-level KPIs

Description	KPI	Target	Progress
Interest on the RDA TIGER support actions (communication / engagement)	# of applications to RDA TIGER support	30 over the project period	104 (<u>35</u> Cascade grants; <u>16</u> external expert/event support; <u>23</u> in-kind; <u>30</u> travel)
RDA TIGER WGs are successfully finished (output)	# of WGs supported which have successfully created their respective outputs	15 Working Groups with successfully finished outputs	3

created) (facilitation, finalisation)			
Produced services have high quality according to users (all services, quality control)	% of positive (>7.5/10) rating in user feedback	95% positive rating over all services	96.1%
RDA TIGER WG outputs have high level of interest and potential impact (dissemination / WG onboarding)	Average (over outputs) # of unique downloads/views of the outputs/yr during project time	500	423
External service provision has been successful (management)	# of provided travel grants	15	23
External service provision has been successful (management)	# of provided 3rd party grants (cascade grants)	6	7
External service provision has been successful (management)	# of consultant support provided	6	9
External service provision has been successful (management)	# of adoption grants	6	7
Landscape follow-up and engagement has provided new members to RDA to participate in the RDA TIGER WGs. (engagement)	# of participants in RDA TIGER WGs, who have not been earlier RDA members	50	219

Interest on the RDA TIGER support actions (communication / engagement): That the project achieved a far larger figure than the original KPIs indicates both the success of the project in terms of promoting the services available and the levels of interest in them in the

RDA community; however, it seems likely that the original KPI target of 30 applications was significantly lower than it should have been (i.e., had the project achieved only 30 applications over the project lifecycle, this would have represented a very low level of interest with the community and demonstrated that more effort would need to have been dedicated to promote them).

RDA TIGER WGs are successfully finished (output created) (facilitation, finalisation): At the time of writing, just three RDA TIGER-supported WGs have produced endorsed Recommendations: WGs are the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG, the Global Open Research Commons International Model (GORC IM) WG and the National PID Strategies WG. The AIDV WG, notably, produced four separate Recommendations, each requiring support from RDA TIGER to get through the endorsement process, whereas WGs typically produce just one endorsed Recommendation in their lifecycles. Additionally, two RDA TIGER-supported WGs are in the process of putting their draft Recommendations through the endorsement process; these groups are the RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) WG and the Wind Energy Community Standards WG. Though this is well below the KPI target set for the project, in the coming months and/or first half of 2026, a further 10 WGs are on track to produce draft Recommendations to put through the endorsement process.⁴³ With the end of the project RDA TIGER is unable to support these WGs in the final stages of their lifecycles; however, we are confident that the efforts made by RDA TIGER, in particular the facilitation service, over the final few months of the project will ensure that these WGs are in as good a position as possible in order to continue their work into 2026 and successfully produce their Recommendations.

Produced services have high quality according to users (all services, quality control): This KPI was analysed against responses to the question “Overall, how satisfied are you with the RDA TIGER service you have received/are receiving?” in project sole feedback form. In order to calculate the percentage figure, percentage values were assigned to the feedback form’s list of dropdown responses, i.e., Very Satisfied=100%; Satisfied=80%; Neutral=60%; Unsatisfied=40%; Very Unsatisfied=20%; I don't know=n/a. As noted above, the project did not receive any Unsatisfied or Very Unsatisfied responses to the form.

RDA TIGER WG outputs have a high level of interest and potential impact (dissemination / WG onboarding): This KPI focused on the impact of outputs produced by RDA TIGER-supported WGs during the project. Outputs tracked here were only those which had been officially recognised by RDA as either Recommendations, Supporting Outputs or Other

⁴³ This prediction is based on facilitators’ close interactions with the WGs in question. These WGs are: Common Application Programming Interface (API) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) WG, RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG, Building Immune Digital Twins WG, Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG, RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG, FAIR Mappings WG, Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG, Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG), FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG, and Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG.

Outputs.⁴⁴ As is RDA protocol, any of these types of outputs are assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and deposited in the Zenodo repository. In order to produce the figure for this KPI, the Views total of each output was calculated. The average views figure for the five Recommendations which were produced by RDA TIGER-supported WGs mentioned above was 423, slightly below the overall target KPI. However, it is worth noting that if we include all outputs (i.e., Recommendations, Supporting Outputs or Other Outputs) produced by RDA TIGER-supported WGs, the average views figure jumps to 713. See Table 10. in section 5 below for a full list of outputs and their respective DOIs.

External service provision has been successful (management): The ‘# of provided travel grants’ KPI was met via two open calls for travel grants, one with a deadline of 2nd June 2025 and a second with a deadline of 31st August 2025, to facilitate travel to International Data Week in Brisbane, Australia. 14 travel grants were awarded across the two calls; however, due a change in their circumstances, one awardee had to decline the grant in the weeks leading up to IDW25. Efforts were made to reallocate this extra budget to another applicant who the Selection Committee deemed worthy of the award; however, there was not sufficient time for this individual to arrange travel and registration in time, so the total awarded travel grants was 13. In addition to this, part of the support for the Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG) workshop which took place in Vienna, Austria in February 2025 included support to cover part of the travel costs for 10 workshop participants (see section 2.3 of D1.4 Final Report On The External And Direct Support Provision And Lessons Learned for further detail on this), bringing the overall total to 23.

The following three KPIs listed in Table X. above, ‘# of provided 3rd party grants (cascade grants)’, ‘# of consultant support provided’, and ‘# of adoption grants’ were all met during the project; again, D1.4 Final Report On The External And Direct Support Provision And Lessons Learned⁴⁵ provides further detail on the processes and recipients of these supports.

The final KPI in Table 6 above, ‘Landscape follow-up and engagement has provided new members to RDA to participate in the RDA TIGER WGs (engagement)’ describes a cumulative target of 50 across all WGs. In total, 219 new RDA members joined RDA TIGER-supported WGs during the project’s lifetime (in order to ensure accuracy regarding this figure, in cases where the RDA TIGER support started after the WG was endorsed, new RDA members were counted from the date of the RDA TIGER support commencement, not the initiation of the WG). See section 4.3 below for more detail on the impact of the Landscape & Engagement service and its associated KPIs.

⁴⁴ Find information on the distinction between these types of outputs on the RDA website here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/> and here: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/recommendations-guidelines/rda-policy-and-norms-for-rda-outputs/>

⁴⁵ Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D1.4: Final report on the external and direct support provision and lessons learned. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17876865>

4.2. Communications Service (WP2) KPIs

This section reports on progress against the list of internal WP2 KPIs set in D2.2⁴⁶ based on a suggested approach outlined in the Grant Agreement. WP2 KPIs were set at 2 levels: a) project level KPIs addressing overall service awareness (section 4.2.1 below), and b) activities carried out as part of the communication service provision to RDA WGs (section 4.2.2 below). This section lists supporting resources and activities to showcase how the KPIs were addressed, and outlines how KPIs evolved and were adapted in order to meet the RDA community's expectations and needs, and to align with RDA WG workflows and processes.

A detailed report of the communication service provision and processes is available at D2.4 Overview of the Communication Service Provision and Lessons Learned⁴⁷.

4.2.1. Project level Communication KPIs

During the lifetime of RDA TIGER, WP2 KPIs at the broad, project-wide level were tracked as part of regular WP6 meetings, while specific implementation was managed in dedicated WP2 meetings taking place every two weeks, with RDA TIGER facilitators present. This section presents an overview with relevant resources and activities corresponding to the KPIs. A key set of activities for project and service awareness was the wide range of webinars delivered which:

- a. Provided information and practical advice on the available RDA TIGER support opportunities;
- b. Promoted the RDA Knowledge Base;
- c. Enabled synergies in a series of thematic, cross-fertilisation webinars, and;
- d. Engaged national networks in a webinar series aiming to embed and promote the WG outputs to RDA regions and communities at the national level.

The analysis of progress against the KPIs is presented below.

KPI WP2a Number of events at which RDA TIGER is presented

Description: Presentation of RDA TIGER in third party events during the project lifetime

Target: 5

Result: 15⁴⁸

Comments: This KPI covers conferences, plenaries, and other third party events. The KPI was met and surpassed, as WP2 set out to present the TIGER activities across Europe with the intention of increasing the membership of the WGs and RDA in general by disseminating outside of the existing RDA community, and engaging with as many relevant stakeholders as possible beyond the immediate RDA membership.

⁴⁶ Delipalta. (2023). RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991152>

⁴⁷ Delipalta, A., Minichiello, F., Halbert, G., Allison, R., Sharma, C. (2025). RDA TIGER D2.4 Overview of the Communication Service Provision and Lessons Learned. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877228>

⁴⁸ See RDA TIGER D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs Annex 1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

KPI WP2b Number of webinars held around open calls per year of the project

Description: Webinars / drop-in sessions held around RDA TIGER Open Calls

Target: 3

Result: 6 (total)

- 2023:
 - [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation First Informational Webinar](#)
 - [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation Second Informational Webinar](#)
 - [RDA TIGER Call for Facilitation Third Informational Webinar](#)
- 2024:
 - [RDA TIGER Cascade Grants 2024 Informational Webinar](#)
 - [RDA TIGER Drop-In Session For Open Call Application Support](#)
- 2025:
 - [RDA TIGER Cascade Grants 2025 Informational Webinar](#)

Comments: During the first year of the project, as per KPI expectation, three informational webinars were held. In subsequent years, and based on existing high demand for RDA TIGER services, established, unchanged processes for RDA TIGER application submissions, existing recordings of informational material, offline advice and information provision by the TIGER team, and most importantly, the overall establishment of the RDA TIGER project as an initiative, two webinars were held in 2024 and one in 2025. By 2025, RDA TIGER had been integrated in RDA and the support on offer was widely known by the community.

KPI WP2c Numbers of webinars held around other initiatives per year of the project

Description: Webinars / drop-in sessions held around other RDA TIGER-related initiatives

Target: 3

Result: 23

- 2023
 - [New RDA working group on Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\) - kick off meeting](#)
 - [New RDA Working Group on Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data - kick off meeting](#)
 - [Data Representation in Chemistry and Materials WG - kick-off meeting](#)
 - [New RDA working group on FAIRification of genome sequence annotations \(tracks\) - Kickoff meetings in September](#)
- 2024
 - [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Semantic Interoperability](#)
 - [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – \(Meta\)Data Standards](#)
 - [From policy to implementation technologies | The EOSC-FUTURE/RDA AIDV-WG's outputs framing Lifetime Omics data visitation technologies](#)
 - [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – FAIR/TRUST/CARE Adoption](#)
 - [The state of Open Science in Slovenia](#)
- 2025
 - [The RDA Knowledge Base Beta Launch](#)
 - [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #1](#)
 - [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on & Feedback Session #2](#)

- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Workshop \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Launch \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on Session \(Morning Session\)](#)
- [RDA Knowledge Base Hands-on Session \(Afternoon Session\)](#)
- [RDA in the Baltics Webinar](#)
- [RDA in Denmark](#)
- RDA and the Polish Data Community ([post](#) and slides for the event: Lehtsalu, L. (2025, June 30). *RDA and the Polish Data Community*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15773023>)
- [RDA in Ireland: RDA Groups showcase](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Making mappings FAIR](#)
- [RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Repositories, trustworthiness and certification](#)
- [RDA in Europe Summit \(event in which final outputs and achievements of RDA TIGER were presented\)](#)

Comments: This KPI was met by organising numerous webinars around RDA TIGER initiatives. Specifically: 1) a series of cross-fertilisation webinars thematically organised which brought together various TIGER-supported WGs, 2) webinars supporting the kick-off of new RDA WGs in order to attract members, 3) events introducing the RDA Knowledge Base and collecting feedback on the tool, and 4) a series of regional webinars linking RDA outputs to the RDA's regional communities.

KPI WP2d Report and update on report

Description: Best practice guide

Target: 1 report at M12, and 1 update at month 36

Result: [Document available on Zenodo](#).

Comment: A guide specifically tailored for facilitators, co-chairs, and community managers working with RDA (Research Data Alliance) Working Groups (WGs). Drawing on lessons from the RDA TIGER project, it provides insight into how facilitation can accelerate WG effectiveness, help navigate RDA structures, and maximise impact.

4.2.2. Working Group-specific Communication KPIs

Deliverable 2.2 outlined internal WP2-specific KPIs for each specific supported WG per WG stage. This section describes the evolution of these KPIs and provides a report of corresponding activities.

4.2.2.1. KPI update and evolution

KPIs set per WG stage

At the project kick-off stage and at the time of writing D2.2, the RDA TIGER project was still building its portfolio of supported WGs, and therefore did not yet have a clear idea of the

ratio of supported WGs per WG lifecycle stage. As RDA TIGER guided 14 WGs from initiation (rather than starting support in later stages), and given the 18-month WG lifespan, 10 WGs are reaching their final stage (C3) in December 2025 or early 2026. Therefore, communication activities for a number of supported WGs in C3 cannot be carried out, as WG output finalisation will take place after the end of the funding period.

Frequency of activity

The KPIs drafted at kick-off stage suggested a frequency of activities that was not feasible or in alignment with RDA WG workflows, and that was therefore not required in practice. Specifically, weekly sharing of WG content for all 23 supported WGs was not always possible, as content was developed at a different pace for each WG (i.e., most did not meet weekly), and therefore there was no available content for publication for each WG at such frequency.

The initial intention for these suggested weekly KPIs was to increase WG visibility and drive engagement; however, throughout the course of the project and as the WP2 team refined workflows, communications focused on WG updates that aligned with the timeframes of the supported RDA WGs, their processes and needs, and also on WG requests for communications support. Promotion of milestone activities such as calling the community to join a new WG, review outputs in Community Review, attend WG Plenary sessions, and to provide feedback when required took place at the appropriate times for each supported WG at the request and direction of WG co-chairs, and with the joint oversight of WP5 and WP2.

Revision of means for achieving intended outcome

For WGs in stage C1 (Group initiation), D2.2 set KPIs with a focus on ‘Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership’ via social media posts, website posts and participation in events (KPIs 2.1 - 2.4). These activities were carried out in particular through the organisation of kick-off meetings that were publicised on the RDA website and on social media with a call for action for the broader community to take part, and examples are noted in section 4.2.2.2. below. However, for the most part, WG co-chairs preferred and requested direct communication and invitations issued to specific individuals and communities. These direct invitations to participate (often based on the landscape reports provided by WP3) were sent by email.

Moreover, all RDA TIGER supported WGs in the C1 stage were consistently included in the corresponding month in RDA Newsletters (see analysis in section 4.2.2.2. below).

4.2.2.2. Activities carried out and progress report

This section describes the WG-specific KPIs as provided in D2.2 against WGs in the corresponding lifecycle/service stage, indicating communication activities that were carried out at the request of the WGs at milestone stages of their lifecycle.

For context, Figure 7 below presents an overview of RDA WGs’ lifecycles and the respective RDA TIGER service stages.

Figure 7. RDA TIGER Services per Work Package and Working Group stage

KPI 2.1 Social media sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - social media

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments: Calls for membership for WGs starting were published via RDA social media channels, in particular in relation to kick-off webinars, at the request of WGs. Weekly posts for each WG were not feasible, as WG content developed in various paces.

Example posts:

- [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) Working Group](#)
- [GORC II kick-off meeting amplification / invite](#)
- [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) Working Group kick off meeting amplification / invite](#)
- [RDA Reproducibility checklist WG in community review](#)

KPI 2.2 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - website posts

Target: Sharing of Group idea and call for membership on 3 partner websites (icl-RDA news items)

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments: This type of outreach took place by posting calls for new members on the RDA website on dedicated WG pages and via direct communication with individuals/organisations identified during the landscape analysis, services, potential members identified either by the facilitators or the co-chairs and WG members.

Examples of website posts:

- [Kick-off of the Building Immune Digital Twins Working Group](#)
- [Join the Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities](#)

[WG Kick-off Meeting](#)

- [Kick-off of the Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data Working Group](#)

KPI 2.3 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - events

Target: Presentation in at least 1 event (RDA or 3rd party)

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments: WG outputs were promoted across third party events and conferences attended by the RDA TIGER consortium throughout the project; examples are provided in KPI 2.11 below.

Supported WG kick-off meetings were promoted as upcoming events on the RDA website.

Example events:

- [New RDA working group on Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\) – kick off meeting](#)
- [New RDA Working Group on Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data – kick off meeting](#)
- [New RDA working group on FAIRification of genome sequence annotations \(tracks\) – Kickoff meetings in September](#)

KPI 2.4 Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - newsletters

Target: At least 1 item/month included in the RDA Global newsletter

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments:

- **2023**
 - [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations Working Group \(DSTS_CS-WG\) - in Community Review in community review promotion in RDA Newsletter in July 2023](#)
 - [RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) WG Case Statement promotion in RDA Newsletter in September 2023](#)
 - [RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG endorsement promotion in RDA Newsletter in October 2023](#)
- **2024**
 - [Harmonised Terminologies and Schemas for FAIR data in Materials Science and Related Domains Working Group Case Statement publication promotion in RDA Newsletter in January 2024](#)
 - [Wind Energy Community Standards Working Group Case Statement for community review promotion in RDA Newsletter in February 2024](#)
 - [FAIRification of Genomic Annotation New Working Group Case Statement in Community Review promotion in RDA Newsletter in March 2024](#)
 - [Building Immune Digital Twins Community Review deadline reminder in RDA Newsletter in April 2024](#)
 - [Community Review reminder for Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities and Small Uncrewed Aircraft and](#)

- [Autonomous Platforms Data new WGs in RDA Newsletter in May 2024](#)
- [Reminder for Community Review for Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities in RDA Newsletter in June 2024](#)
- [\(TRSPs\) and FAIR Mappings WG in Community Review announcements in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
- [Health data commons new WG in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
- **2025**
 - [GORC International Implementations \(GORC II WG\) and Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) Working Groups in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in January 2025](#)
 - [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) Working Group in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in March 2025](#)
 - [RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in April 2025](#)
 - [Common Application Programming Interface \(API\) for machine-actionable Data Management Plans \(maDMPs\) WG and Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II \(MaLDReTH II\) WG new WG features in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)

KPI 2.5 WG page unique views

Target: 30 unique page views during C1 stage.

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments: This KPI could not be meaningfully tracked across the project lifespan due to the RDA web platform migration and associated data gaps. In addition, many WGs in the C1 stage do not have a public web page while carrying out preparatory Statement of Work activities. Related service impact can be demonstrated through the increase in supported new RDA and WG members as reported in section 4.3, figure 8 of this report.

KPI 2.6 New WG members

Target: 20 (new) WG members by the end of the project

WG Stage: C1 (WG starting)

Progress and Comments: See Annex 2

KPI 2.7 Unique group page views

Target: 30 per month

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments: See comment in KPI 2.5 above.

KPI 2.8 Creation of Group Collaterals

Target: at least 5 communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

- [‘Introducing the Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities Working Group’ video and promotional campaign](#)
- I-ADOPT Variable Modelling Workshops promotional campaign ^{49, 50, 51}
- [Introducing the MOMSI Landscape Dashboard: A Tool for Mapping Multi-Omics Standards promotional campaign](#)
- [Repository Services - developing trust in the ecosystem \(TRSPs WG promotional campaign\)](#)
- [Shaping Responsible AI: Four New Recommendations from the AIDV Working Group](#)
- [Get Involved: RDA TIGER Calls to Action from the 24th RDA Plenary Meeting \(multiple WGs\)](#)

KPI 2.9 Group mention in RDA Global newsletter

Target: 1 per quarter

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

- **2023**
 - GORC IM WG co-located event promoted in RDA Newsletters in February 2023^{52, 53}
 - [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers \(TRSPs\) - Plenary session recap by WG Facilitator promoted at RDA Newsletter in November 2023](#)
- **2024**
 - [RDA Council Endorsement for the Wind Energy Community Standards Working Group announcement in RDA Newsletter in May 2024](#)
 - [Endorsed Group announcement of FAIRification of Genomic Annotations Working Group in RDA Newsletter in June 2024](#)
 - [Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG endorsement announcement in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
 - [Building Immune Digital Twins WG endorsement announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
 - [Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG and Community-based Catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Services Providers \(TRSPs\) WG endorsement announcements in RDA Newsletter in September 2024](#)
 - [Health Data Commons GORC Profile New Working Group announcement in RDA Newsletter in December 2024](#)
 - [Alignment of Multilingual Vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities Working Group \(SSH Vocabs\) feature in RDA newsletter in December 2024](#)

⁴⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310627672135553024/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7304852371245858816/>

⁵¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7298237496407085057>

⁵² <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda-month-review-decade-data-plenary-20-tab-election-results-and-more>

⁵³ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/rda-month-review-plenary-20-special-issue-and-other-news>

- 2025

- [Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations by the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG output in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in February 2025](#)
- [FAIR Mappings Working Group feature in RDA Newsletter in February 2025](#)
- [GORC II WG feature in RDA Newsletter in March 2025](#)
- [Post-plenary WG session feature \(multiple WGs\), and The RDA Working Group on Ethics in Agricultural Data survey promotion in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [Building Immune Digital Twins Working Group and HarmonisedMatChem Working Group external expert open calls in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [KICK OFF MEETING: GORC International Implementations Working Group \(GORC II WG\) in RDA Newsletter and website in April 2025](#)
- [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) & Research Software Alliance Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) Working Group 'other' output feature in RDA Newsletter in May 2025](#)
- [Introducing the MOMSI Landscape Dashboard: A Tool for Mapping Multi-Omics Standards feature in RDA Newsletter in May 2025](#)
- [MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-based Dashboard Tool Supporting Output from Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) Working Group in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)

KPI 2.10 Social Media Mentions

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

- Example posts:
 - RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG amplification^{54, 55, 56}
 - [Plenary session promotion \(multiple WGs\)](#)
 - [Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG meeting amplification](#)
 - [RDA-CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services \(DSTS\) for Crisis Situations Working Group survey amplification](#)
 - [Multi-omics Metadata Standards and Interoperability \(MOMSI\) Working Group](#)
 - Ethics in Agricultural Data WG survey amplification^{57, 58}

⁵⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363827147972452353>

⁵⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7349331630253060096>

⁵⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7363827147972452353>

⁵⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7328751450065375233>

⁵⁸ https://x.com/RDA_Europe/status/1917866861250650336?s=20

- [BIDT activity promotion \(call for experts amplification for expert grant\)](#)
- [HarmonisedMatChem Working Group activity promotion \(call for experts amplification for expert grant\)](#)
- [Management and alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the SSH plenary session promotion](#)

KPI 2.11 Event presence

Target: Participation/promotion in at least five events per year (not including RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc).

WG Stage: C2 (WG Work period)

Progress and Comments:

- Example WG promotion:
 - [RDA TIGER lightning talk and poster at LIBER 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
 - [RDA TIGER poster and lightning talk at EGI 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
 - [RDA TIGER talk on the impact of RDA outputs to EOSC \(multiple WGs\) and 'Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics' panel discussion focused on the RDA AIDV WG at OSFair 2025.](#)
 - [IDCC2025 lightning talk \(multiple WGs\) and poster presentation \(multiple WGs\)](#)
 - [Open Science Today and Tomorrow conference organized in Vilnius, Lithuania in October 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)

KPI 2.12 Group-Internal newsletter and/or bulletin

Target: 1 per month

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: Individual WG newsletters were not pursued, as the content relevant for each WG would be duplicated from the RDA Global Newsletter, and the new web platform allowed for efficient *ad hoc* news posts also addressing time-critical announcements. Internal WG communications spotlighting specific items of interest were carried out by RDA TIGER for WGs across C1-C3 using mailing lists and the RDA web posting functionality often multiple times a month. Example internal communications process is presented in Figure 10 in Annex 3.

KPI 2.13 Unique group page views

Target: 50 for the duration of the project

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: See comment in KPI 2.5 above; also, supported WGs at stage C3 span beyond the end of the RDA TIGER project.

KPI 2.14 Creation of Group collaterals

Target: at least 2 communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

- GORC International Model Communique drafting and production for two types of

stakeholders, first created in 2023, updated in October 2025^{59, 60}

- National PID Strategies WG checklist visualisations and [infographic](#), and [white paper](#).

KPI 2.15 Group mention in RDA Global newsletter

Target: 1 per Output stage

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

- **2023**
 - [National PID Strategies Working Group - Final Recommendations promoted in RDA Newsletter in September 2023](#)
 - [GORC International Model Working Group - New Supporting Output In community review promoted in RDA Newsletters in September 2023](#)
 - [GORC International Model Working Group output endorsements promoted in RDA Newsletter in October 2023](#)
 - [GORC International Model Working Group output finalisation communication materials promoted in RDA Newsletter in November 2023](#)
- **2024**
 - [GORC International Model WG and Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG Recommendations in community review announcements in RDA Newsletter in July 2024](#)
 - [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG: AI Bill of Rights Recommendation, and Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and DV recommendations in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
 - [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools recommendation in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
 - [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG: Shared Citation Library supporting output in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in August 2024](#)
 - [RDA-OfR Mapping the Digital Landscape WG: Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools recommendation in community review announcement in RDA Newsletter in September 2024](#)
 - [The Global Open Research Commons International Model final output mention in RDA Newsletter in October 2024](#)
 - [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools final output mention in RDA Newsletter in November 2024](#)
- **2025**
 - [MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-based Dashboard Tool supporting output in community review in RDA Newsletter in April 2025](#)
 - [Four new recommendations from the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) Working Group feature in RDA Newsletter in June 2025](#)

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

⁶⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341560>

- [NEW BLOG — Shaping Responsible AI: Four New Recommendations from the AIDV Working Group By the Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG feature in RDA Newsletter in August 2025](#)

KPI 2.16 Social media mentions

Target: Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels

WP Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

- Example posts
 - [Cascade grant deliverable presentation for supported WG GORC IM WG](#)
 - [Adoption story promotion for GORC IM WG](#)
 - [Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG General WG promotion](#)
 - Plenary session promotion (multiple WGs)^{61, 62}
 - [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG](#) activity promotion^{63, 64}
 - [RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group output community review amplification](#)

KPI 2.17 Event presence

Target: Participation/promotion in at least two events per year (not including RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc.)

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments:

- Example event participation highlighting multiple supported WGs
 - [EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG](#) Panel ‘Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics’ at OSFair 2025. Panel composed of 2 WG co-chairs (Natalie Meyers, Elif Ecmekci), chaired by Alex Delipalta, Project Coordinator^{65, 66}
 - [RDA TIGER poster at LIBER 2025 \(multiple WGs\)](#)
 - RDA TIGER [poster](#) and [lightning talk](#) at EGI 2025 (multiple WGs)

KPI 2.18 Adoption outreach

Target: Target at least 2 adopters for each Recommendation via any means

WG Stage: C3 (WG end period)

Progress and Comments: All RDA TIGER WGs at finalisation stage provided a list of adopters, which have been contacted by WP2. At the time of writing, three adoption stories have been

⁶¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7384367297400053760>

⁶² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7383325138823393280>

⁶³ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7348600501640290304>

⁶⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7338864695115718656>

⁶⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7373982367184494592>

⁶⁶ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/panels/data-for-ai-from-readiness-to-ethics>

completed as part of this outreach for the GORC initiative^{67,68,69}, with multiple ongoing conversations with adopters towards the production of more adoption stories, specifically for the AIDV and I-ADOPT WGs. All adoption stories produced with the support of RDA TIGER are listed on the [project web page](#).

4.3. Landscape Analysis Service (WP3) KPIs

The RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement Service (WP3) provides Landscape Analysis Reports to WGs who request this service. This service aims to support greater WG engagement, visibility and impact of their outputs. The report, based on desk research engagement with RDA TIGER partner’s extensive network, as well as liaison with WP4 and contribution from the Knowledge Base supports WGs in identifying relevant stakeholders or initiatives in their related domains.

Table 7. WP3 Working Group KPIs

Description	KPI	Target	Progress
Interest on the RDA TIGER of the Landscape Analysis Service	# of RDA TIGER WGs request Landscape analysis service	-	7
Produced Landscape Analysis Service have high quality according to users	% of positive (>7.5/10) rating in user feedback	95% positive rating over all services	100%
Landscape follow-up and engagement has provided new members to RDA to participate in the RDA TIGER WGs.	# of participants in RDA TIGER WGs, who have not been earlier RDA members	50	219

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the Landscape Analysis Service (WP3), which evaluate the success of the service, are

- # of entries in the landscape service database
- # of RDA TIGER WGs request Landscape analysis service
- % positive rating in user feedback
- # of participants in RDA TIGER WGs who have not been earlier RDA members

⁶⁷

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-gorc-model-reason/>

⁶⁸

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-gorc-model-surf/>

⁶⁹

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/adoption-stories/adopting-the-global-open-research-commons-model-the-case-of-eosc-data-commons/>

Table 7 above shows the main WP3 KPIs. However, other success indicators of the Landscape Analysis & Engagement Service have been omitted:

- # of new potential WG members identified;
- # of international relevant initiatives listed.

The value of the landscape analysis service is most accurately assessed in the satisfaction levels of the WGs co-chairs, captured through the user feedback survey. Moreover, initiatives related to Open Science (OS) are continuously documented and published through the WP3 deliverables: the 2023 ‘D3.1 - OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets’⁷⁰, the 2024 ‘D3.4 - Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets’⁷¹ and the 2025 ‘MS10 - Updated Landscape analysis for project final period’⁷². Two final deliverables will further expand the collection of gathered initiatives and will be published in the [RDA TIGER Zenodo Community](#) at the end of 2025: D3.5 - Final report on engagement and landscape monitoring, lessons learned and D3.6 - Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC.

During the RDA TIGER project period, 7 out of the 20 supported WGs requested a Landscape Analysis report, with two still in progress at the time of writing, demonstrating the interest of this service among the RDA WGs. The objectives of the Landscape Analysis report are diverse and depend on the expectations of each WG’s request. The main purposes have been identified as:

- Identifying potential adopters or implementers;
- Searching for new members;
- Establishing contacts to socialise outputs or conduct surveys;
- Exploring a broader range of topic-related initiatives to enhance WGs’ knowledge.

Despite specific requests to those WG co-chairs who received Landscape Analysis Reports to provide feedback on the service and the reports, only two responses relating to these were received, both of which were ‘Very Satisfied’ (one respondent selected ‘Landscape and Engagement’ in response to the question ‘Which RDA TIGER service would you like to provide feedback for?’; the other selected ‘Facilitation’ but noted in a free text response that the WG also received a Landscape and Analysis report, which they noted was a “welcome addition”). When the Landscape Analysis Reports were delivered, recipients responded positively and expressed their gratitude at receiving them; however, as this didn’t result in any formal feedback via the form, this was not counted in the overall total.

The presence of RDA TIGER WG members who had not been earlier RDA members since the RDA TIGER project’s start reflect not only the interest of the group’s topic to the community, but also indicate the significant impact of the RDA TIGER services on engaging new

⁷⁰ Rettberg, N., Asmi, A., Molloy, L., Hugo, W., Delipalta, A., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

⁷¹ Molloy, L. (2024). RDA TIGER D3.4 Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

⁷² GRAU, N. (2025). RDA TIGER MS10: Updated Landscape Analysis for Project Final Period. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

participants. The impact of the RDA TIGER support on WGs engagement depends and differs from the start of the service according to the WGs’ activity. Indeed, some WGs’ received RDA TIGER support once already started and some from their inception.

The date that members of RDA TIGER-supported WGs joined the RDA were collected by going through the members’ pages of each WG, and accessing each of the members’ profile pages, which contains this data. The data was collected on September 19th 2025, and is available in the Annex. The number of RDA TIGER WGs members according to their RDA membership date, before and after the RDA TIGER support started for each group, and the percentage of new RDA membership by RDA TIGER WGs is represented in Figure 8. This figure shows the number and ratio of RDA TIGER WGs’ members according to their RDA membership year (before and since the RDA TIGER support’s start).

Figure 8. RDA WG member numbers

10 WGs received the RDA TIGER support after the WG’s activity started and 13 WGs received the support from their inception, and are represented respectively in the left and right part of Figure 3. The three RDA TIGER WGs with the highest proportion of new RDA membership are the [Building Immune Digital Twins WG](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/building-immune-digital-twins-wg/activity/)⁷³, with almost one third of new RDA membership (74%), [FAIRification of Genomic Annotation WG](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fairification-genomic-annotations-wg/activity/)⁷⁴ with 51% of new RDA membership and the [Wind Energy Community Standards WG](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/wind-energy-community-standards-wg/activity/)⁷⁵, with 38%. of new RDA membership. The median of the percentage of new RDA membership by RDA WGs which received RDA TIGER support after their start is 15%, while this amount is 25% for the other RDA TIGER-supported WGs (i.e., those who received support from their outset). The 10% of difference between the two supported groups show the concrete impact of the RDA TIGER support in attracting new RDA memberships into WGs. In total, the number of new RDA members since the beginning of RDA TIGER support for all the RDA WGs supported, 269 new eligible members, or 219 if each counted once.

⁷³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/building-immune-digital-twins-wg/activity/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fairification-genomic-annotations-wg/activity/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/wind-energy-community-standards-wg/activity/>

4.4. Outputs Service (WP4) KPIs

4.4.1. Knowledge Base website metrics

The Knowledge Base was officially launched on October 6th, 2025. In connection with this, the Knowledge Base was moved to a permanent web domain from its previous demo environment. This limits the website metrics that are possible to track, e.g. for number of page visits and downloads. However, in its two months, the Knowledge Base already attracted nearly 800 visits from different parts of the world. Figure 9 shows that the great majority of visitors were from either Europe or North America, indicating that outreach and communications may need to be carried out to increase uptake in other regions of the world.

Table 8 below provides more detailed metrics on the behaviour of visitors to the RDA Knowledge Base (kb-rda.org) in the first month since its launch. Page bounce rates (i.e. users that left the website after only visiting one page) were 24%. Although this may seem like a large number, according to figures by Databox,⁷⁶ the median rate across different industries was roughly 60%. The numbers may be further explained by the fact that the search and discovery functionality of the RDA-KB (RDA Discovery) can be accessed in full without leaving the landing page of the website, which links directly to it.

Also potentially instructive is the fact that most visitors came to the site through direct access (e.g. entering the URL directly into the browser, rather than clicking a link on a different website). This may indicate that direct communication regarding the RDA-KB (e.g., through emails or in workshops) was relatively effective, or that promotion via e.g. the RDA website and other channels may need to be increased.

⁷⁶ <https://databox.com/website-traffic-benchmarks-by-industry#bounce-rate> (accessed 01-12-2025)

Figure 9. Knowledge Base website metrics

Table 8. Knowledge Base metrics since launch (06/10—11/12, 2025)

Metric	Description	Result
Page visits	Overall # visits to the Knowledge Base website (kb-rda.org)	773
Page views	# visits to various pages of the website	1,696 total; 1,438 unique
Outlinks	Number of links clicked leading away from the website	45 total; 38 unique
Bounce rate	% of visitors that left the website after one page	24%
Channels	Through which channels users navigated to the site (e.g. clicking on website or social network links, or entering the URL directly)	Direct access: 521 Websites: 221 Search engines: 27 Social networks: 4

4.5. Facilitation Service (WP5) KPIs

As indicated in D5.2 First Evaluation of the Facilitation Services,⁷⁷ the Facilitation Service KPIs (or ‘Quality Indicators’ as they are termed in section 3.2.2 of D5.2) were compiled by the facilitators in WP5 meetings and reported to WP6. Table 9 below contains both the interim June 2024 totals, as reported in D5.2, and the final totals as compiled at the time of writing.

⁷⁷ O'Connor, R. (2024). D5.2 First Evaluation of the Facilitation Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12599362>

Further explanation of each is provided in the paragraphs under the table. These KPIs do not have targets set.

Table 9. Facilitation service KPIs

KPI	Description	June 2024 total	Final total
5.1	Number of WGs supported by WP5	14 (10 via Open Call application; 4 RDA TIGER Pilot Demonstrator WGs)	20
5.2	Number of virtual meetings organised	30 (20 at RDA P22, 10 outside RDA Plenary)	49
5.3	Number of physical meetings organised	5 (at RDA Plenary 21, in Salzburg, Austria)	18
5.4	Number of WG outputs finalised	0 (no supported WGs have yet completed this stage of their life cycle)	12
5.5	Number of WG case statements supported	11 (5 endorsed, 3 in approval process, 3 in draft prior to submission)	12
5.6	Number of people participating in the WG sessions	-	-

Number of WGs supported by WP5: The final total of WGs receiving support from the Facilitation Service at the end of the RDA TIGER project was 20. This figure comprised 16 WGs which applied for support via the project’s Open Calls and four WGs were the project’s Pilot Demonstrator WGs. These 20 WGs represented a significant proportion of the RDA WGs who were active over the project’s three year lifetime.

Number of virtual meetings organised: This figure comprised the meetings of all WGs receiving Facilitation Service support held at RDA Virtual Plenaries (VPs) along with ‘public’ WG meetings (e.g., kick-off meetings, community consultations, etc.). The breakdown of these figures was as follows:

- RDA VP22: 21 sessions
- RDA VP24: 14 sessions

- Three FAIR Mappings WG kick-off meetings (these were promoted via a private mailing list gathered at RDA VP23 and WG co-chair contacts prior to the WG becoming officially endorsed)
- [Public kick-off meeting](#) of Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) kick-off (Sept 2024)
- [Public kick-off meeting](#) of Building Immune Digital Twins Data WG
- [Public kick-off meeting](#) of Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG
- [Public kick-off meeting](#) of Data Representation in Chemistry and Materials WG (original name of Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG) (Sept 2023)
- Two public kick-off meetings of the FAIRification of Genome Sequence Annotations (tracks) WG (original name of the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG) (Sept 2023):
 - [12th Sept 2023](#)
 - [25th Sept 2023](#)
- Five RDA TIGER Cross-fertilisation webinars on topics of:
 - [Semantic Interoperability](#)
 - [Metadata Standards](#)
 - [FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles](#)
 - [Making mappings FAIR](#)
 - [Repositories, trustworthiness and certification](#)

Number of physical meetings organised: This figure was the total of RDA TIGER Facilitation Service-supported WG sessions which took place at RDA Plenaries 21, 23 and 25 in Salzburg, San Jose and Brisbane respectively. There were five such sessions at RDA P21, 12 at P23, and 14 at P25.

Number of WG outputs finalised: This figure consists of the total number of Outputs (Recommendations, Supporting Outputs and Other Outputs) produced by RDA TIGER WGs who have received Facilitation Service support. The total at the time of writing is 12 (comprising six Recommendations, four Supporting Outputs and two Other Outputs). However, as pointed out in section 4.1 above on the project-wide KPIs, specifically in relation to the 'RDA TIGER WGs are successfully finished (output created) (facilitation, finalisation)' KPI a further 10 WGs are expected to finalise their Recommendations in the final months of 2025 or in the first half of 2026.

Number of WG case statements supported: Of the 20 WGs that received Facilitation Service support, 12 were successfully supported through this process, with two at the time of writing currently undergoing this process. The remaining six WGs were endorsed prior to support beginning. No WGs who received RDA TIGER Facilitation Service support have failed to have their WG endorsed by RDA Council. Note the term 'case statement' has now been superseded in RDA since the beginning of the RDA TIGER project by 'Statement of Work'. This has not resulted in a change in the type of information required from RDA WGs at their

outset; rather it was done to ensure that both RDA WGs and IGs were using the same term for this document (instead of Case Statement and Charter, respectively).

As indicated in D5.2, the final KPIs for the Facilitation Service, i.e., ‘**Number of people participating in the WG sessions**’, has not been tracked as the WP5 and WP6 leads decided that without the figures from other RDA WGs on the numbers of people attending WG meetings to compare, there was little value in tracking this for WGs receiving RDA TIGER support.

5. Sustainability, exploitation and impact beyond project lifetime

The RDA TIGER project enabled the four partner institutions to dedicate three years to supporting RDA WGs through this suite of services, in addition to providing funds for the procurement of external experts contributing niche expertise to RDA outputs, and a significant amount in cascade grants for the enrichment and adoption of RDA recommendations.

The high uptake of the RDA TIGER support services over the three years of the project and the consistent positive feedback received from the community highlights the importance of providing targeted support to initiatives like the RDA, which are open to all and reliant on volunteer contributions. The impact of the RDA TIGER support is evident across this deliverable through concrete metrics, surpassing of project KPIs, and through the voice of the community in the feedback collected. This section outlines the sustainability and exploitation paths for the RDA TIGER service suite and project results.

5.1. Sustainability of project results

Deliverable 2.2 ‘Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (version 2.0)’⁷⁸ defines five sustainability models; based on this and with the conclusion of the RDA TIGER funding period, sustainability of the services will be carried out through the routes described below.

5.1.1. Project-based sustainability

Horizon Europe funding

Consortium partners and RDA AISBL in particular has included the provision of facilitation services in its portfolio of applications for Horizon Europe funding under the Work Programme 2025, where topics aligned with the strategy and mission of the RDA, and where the project would benefit from the creation of an RDA WG to broaden the discussion, leverage additional expertise, and work towards the internationalisation of project results. A similar strategy to maintain, further develop and enrich the RDA Knowledge Base through upcoming Horizon Europe funding (depending on successful proposals) is being developed.

⁷⁸ Halbert, G., & Delipalta, A. (2024). RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (version 2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14386006>

These projects have synergies with the RDA Knowledge Base, including software with similar aims and shared code, which makes co-development of these services mutually beneficial. In addition, existing projects and infrastructures have been identified where these synergies already exist. The precise sustainability plans for the Knowledge Base are currently being developed in collaboration with partners.

5.1.2. Document-based sustainability

Beyond the value of the service provision to the supported WGs and its immediate effect on the WGs' efficiency, output quality and overall operation, RDA TIGER has drafted a number of supplementary materials aiming to preserve lessons learned and to enable the community to maintain the level of efficiency in RDA operational procedures beyond the project lifetime. These documents are available from the [RDA TIGER Zenodo Community](#).

RDA TIGER Working Group Facilitation Best Practice Handbook⁷⁹

In acknowledgment of the added value of providing facilitation support to RDA WG co-chairs, and the fact that this type of support will not continue in the same way going forward, the Facilitation team has produced a Facilitation Handbook. The resource describes best practice, tools, engagement techniques and general group facilitation guidance that co-chairs can implement to keep up the pace after the end of the RDA TIGER funding. As the project spent the first year in its lifecycle in a pilot stage, refining and operationalising the support offering and service structure, any future facilitation work can kick off directly with delivery, using the Handbook (and all relevant operational deliverables and reports).

Facilitation Tips & Tools Guide⁸⁰

This resource, which was also developed by the Facilitation Service, provides users with tips and tools that are organisation-neutral and applicable to anyone coordinating collaborative group work. Inspired by the facilitation practices employed in the RDA TIGER project, this resource compiles practical tools, approaches, and considerations to help facilitators plan, run, and sustain productive group activities in any context.

RDA TIGER Welcome Pack⁸¹

The onboarding documentation prepared by WP5, while including RDA TIGER-specific information for the purposes of informing those receiving TIGER support, also outlines key RDA processes and brings together a list of useful links and materials that can be used to familiarise newcomers to RDA and new WG co-chairs.

RDA Templates overview

At the start of RDA TIGER, multiple templates and other standards already existed for RDA-related content. Where templates for outputs that WP4 considers useful for the

⁷⁹ Papadopoulou, A. (2025). RDA Working Group Facilitation Best Practice. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18012145>

⁸⁰ Papadopoulou, A. (2025). Facilitation Tips & Tools Guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18011922>

⁸¹ Papadopoulou, A., Allison, R., Lehtsalu, L., & O'Connor, R. (2025). RDA TIGER Welcome pack - An onboarding guide for RDA Working Groups. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17791908>

abovementioned aims (e.g. WG presentations, reports, branding, etc.) do not exist, are outdated, or not promoted by the RDA, these are drafted and proposed to the RDA Secretariat by WP4. This document aims to provide an overview of existing and planned templates, including their current status and development. To our knowledge, no such overview was available before, and having one should help ensure that all necessary templates are available and up to date. The document is available through the [RDA Knowledge Base](#).

RDA Recommended metadata schema

This resource provides an overview of the metadata to use when depositing RDA materials to Zenodo, or when creating annotations using the RDA Annotator. The overview lists both mandatory metadata (e.g., title, rightsholder, and RDA-related keywords), as well as recommended ones (e.g. language of the resource, RDA Pathway classification, and notes). The resource is available through the [RDA Knowledge Base](#).

RDA vocabularies

This document provides a list of vocabularies specific to RDA-related topics and registries, and are maintained by the RDA community. The document is available through the [RDA Knowledge Base](#).

Standards Development Recommendations from HSBooster

A report aiming to support the WGs identified by RDA TIGER in integrating, engaging, and contributing the WGs outputs to the standards community by presenting an introduction to the standards process and relevant considerations. This is done by providing an introduction to the role of standardisation and its goals, potentially relevant standards bodies for the WGs, and potential challenges that may be faced in pursuing standardisation for the WGs. Specifically, this report aims to answer the questions of: 1. Which standards organisations would be good candidates for the identified WGs? 2. How could future RDA Interest Groups (IG) be targeted to work towards such a goal? The document is available through the [RDA Knowledge Base](#).

RDA TIGER Knowledge Base Support Materials

The Support Materials hosted on the [Knowledge Base](#) feature various materials relevant to RDA users, including those described above in this section. This document base will continue to be maintained past the project, and may be updated and extended as needed, using content-related expertise provided by RDA.

5.1.3. Sustainability via organisations

The RDA TIGER in-kind support services, and in particular certain tasks within the communication and facilitation service, while primarily intended to be maintained through the means described in '5.1.1 'Project-based sustainability' and 5.1.5 'Fee-carrying or sponsored sustainability', continue to be an endeavour that is of high value to the RDA, and are at least partially ingrained into the business as usual processes of RDA and tasks carried

out by the RDA Secretariat. While not to the extent offered by the funded RDA TIGER project, which allowed for significant additional dedicated effort on these activities, support at a less intensive level will continue to be carried out by RDA.

The code base of the RDA TIGER Knowledge Base is a collection of open-source software that is already shared, and will continue to be shared, with other HE-funded projects. The Knowledge Base adopts two related objectives related to future sustainability. These are:

- **RDA Knowledge Base specific assets** (vocabularies, operational instances, applications, content) must remain in the public domain and be available to any end user without cost. Costs may be incurred to provide and maintain the assets.
- **Code assets are open source**, developed with EU funding, and as a Key Exploitable Resource of the RDA TIGER project can be used to establish a revenue stream for a broader product range that includes the RDA Knowledge Base as a community resource.

These open source and public domain assets have and will likely continue to be of use to other HE-funded projects and EOSC-related developments. Co-development opportunities and synergies with several HE-funded projects under consideration for funding in 2026 have also been identified. The added benefit for the sustainability of the Knowledge Base is that shared code with other projects and services facilitates maintenance and continuous bug fixes, as well as the identification of opportunities for further development. The code base and hosting of the Knowledge Base will continue to be maintained by DANS following the end of the project. The project is also identifying opportunities for additional funding and development of the Knowledge Base by other HE-funded projects. An instance of a EOSC Node-based knowledge base platform, with support and maintenance secured for a period until end 2028.

As described in the previous section, the various support materials hosted by the Knowledge Base will also be maintained by the RDA Secretariat and TAB going forward. Technical guidance and user manuals for the Knowledge Base, that are also stored among its support materials, will also be maintained and updated as needed through a combination of resources presented here.

5.1.4. Community sustainability

The legacy and impact of the RDA TIGER project also lies with its supported WGs and the quality and usefulness of their outputs, and through the wider Open Science Community via the uptake and adoption of solutions, contribution to policies, and towards harmonising standards. The table 10 below presents a list of published outputs by supported WGs as of 24 November 2025. As clarified in section 4.1 above, 10 more Recommendations are expected to be published in the final months of 2025/first half of 2026.

Table 10. List of published outputs by RDA TIGER-supported WGs

Output title	Working Group	Output type	DOI	Zenodo views	Date of views figure
The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1	GORC International Model WG	Supporting Output	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099	2649	17/11/2025
The Global Open Research Commons International Model, version 1.1 Model Overview	GORC International Model WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00119	590	17/11/2025
The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1	GORC International Model WG	Supporting Output	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097	1377	17/11/2025
RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist	National PID Strategies WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091	1345	17/11/2025
MOMSI WG Multi-Omics Standard Landscape Review Curation Workflow & Interactive Web-based Dashboard Tool	Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG	Supporting Output	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00133	227	17/11/2025
Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00129	71	17/11/2025
Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and DV	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00122	232	17/11/2025
AI Bill of Rights Recommendation	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00123	167	17/11/2025
Guidance for Informed Consent in the context of Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG	Recommendation	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00121	135	17/11/2025
AIDV Shared Citation Library	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG	Supporting Output	https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00124	54	17/11/2025
Resources for supporting policy change in research institutions in practice	RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS)	Other output	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11529659	662	17/11/2025

Identifying Gaps in Research Software Policy	RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS)	Other output	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16941858	1052	17/11/2025
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5.1.5. Fee-carrying or sponsored sustainability

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Framework for engagement with the private sector
 In the context of this Framework⁸², focused on creating partnerships with the industry, the RDA calls for collaborations with industry partners who, in support of the mission and vision of RDA, provide financial support for the creation and facilitation of RDA WGs. A previous example of such endeavours is the collaboration with Oracle for Research⁸³.

Costing and quantifying the facilitation service

In preparation for potential commercialisation of the RDA TIGER service suite and to better inform integration and potential continuation through the Framework for engagement with the private sector, the project carried out an extensive time-keeping exercise over a period of 4 months aiming to quantify the level of effort required for each WG, per WG lifecycle and service stage⁸⁴. This analysis will feed into FTE and financial costing and tailoring of any potential future service offers under the means described above.

5.2. Exploitation of project results

RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities⁸⁵ identified five Key Exploitable Results (KERs) at project start in 2023: RDA TIGER support structure as a template; Individual TIGER support services as marketable product; Best practice guidelines for facilitation of expert groups; Annotation tool; Landscape analysis. The final RDA TIGER General Assembly in June 2025 reviewed and refined the initial list, and drafted three additional KERs, summarised in table 11. Minimum exploitation plans and potential further exploitation paths, many of which are already being actioned by the consortium as described in section 5.1, are also outlined below.

⁸² The Value of the Research Data Alliance to Industry and the Private Sector:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/stakeholders/industry-and-private-sector/>

⁸³ The RDA and Oracle for Research: Collaboration to accelerate data-driven discovery:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/the-rda-and-oracle-for-research-collaboration-to-accelerate-data-driven-discovery>

⁸⁴

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1wm2esb1ck0EbiGvLYuuiw7-KcG1QkXlWgmqv1vg41wA/edit?gid=982395538#gid=982395538>

⁸⁵ Delipalta. (2023). RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991152>

Table 11. RDA TIGER Key Exploitable Results

KER	Name	Potential users	Lead	KER type	Minimum sustainability	Exploitation paths
1	RDA TIGER support structure model	Other RDA regions/programmes (e.g., TIGRUS) Other organisations with similar structure (e.g., NFDI, LIBER, OpenAIRE, ReSA)	RDA Europe	Community resource, business model, service suite concept	'Menu' (document-based sustainability) of a service suite concept and documentation that can be adapted and offered by RDA regions, and potentially inform other infrastructures	Support documentation, contract templates, service structure templates, WG service agreements are all publicly available and can be directly adopted by future RDA regions launching similar services and by RDA Secretariat. One adoption/adaptation already took place (TIGRUS, RDA US).
2	Individual RDA TIGER support services as marketable product	Funders, industry and other relevant entities, e.g., Data spaces actors within the EOSC ecosystem (paid directly or provided as a service to them, e.g., through a procurement arrangement)	RDA Europe	Fee-carrying, standardised service	Standalone service descriptions available to funders (document-based sustainability)	RDA TIGER project has engaged a range of stakeholders that can potentially leverage the services as part of the RDA framework for engagement with the private sector ⁸⁶ (fee carrying sustainability) or other funding proposals.
2.1	Landscape Service	Funders interested in the RDA community (companies, international organisations or NGOs wishing to leverage RDA as a neutral platform for developing community recommendations for specific FAIR data challenges)	RDA Europe, CODATA	Fee-carrying, standardised service	Standalone service descriptions available to funders (document-based sustainability)	Lessons learned from the landscape support provided under RDA TIGER have enriched the skillset of the consortium, and similar activities will be included in future funding proposals also with a broader scope (e.g., wider national landscape analyses, regional open science analyses, etc), and/or as part of the RDA Framework for engagement with the private sector.
2.2	Facilitation Service	Funders interested in the RDA community (companies, international organisations or NGOs wishing to leverage RDA as a neutral platform for developing community recommendations for specific FAIR data challenges)	RDA Europe	Fee-carrying, standardised service	Standalone service descriptions available to funders (document-based sustainability)	Lessons learned and infrastructure created will be leveraged in future funding proposals and as part of the RDA Framework for engagement with the private sector.

⁸⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/stakeholders/industry-and-private-sector/>

KER	Name	Potential users	Lead	KER type	Minimum sustainability	Exploitation paths
2.3	Communication Service	Funders interested in the RDA community (companies, international organisations or NGOs wishing to leverage RDA as a neutral platform for developing community recommendations for specific FAIR data challenges)	RDA Europe	Fee-carrying, standardised service	Standalone service descriptions available to funders (document-based sustainability)	Materials and templates created can be reused going forward by RDA and WGs themselves; networks engaged and relationships created and continue to be leveraged by RDA. As a service it can continue to be offered to RDA WGs as part of the RDA Framework for engagement with the private sector.
2.4	RDA Working Group Facilitation Best Practice Handbook ⁸⁷	RDA community	RDA Europe	Guideline/recommendation	Zenodo	Guidance that can be leveraged by RDA Secretariat and by WGs and co-chairs themselves.
3	Standardisation Roadmap	RDA community	DANS	Guideline/recommendation	Zenodo	Guidance that can be leveraged by RDA Secretariat and by Working and Interest Groups.
4	Facilitation Tips & Tools Guide ⁸⁸	RDA community Other organisations with similar structure (steering committees, programme committees, working groups)	RDA Europe	Guideline/recommendation (reputational) Community resource	Zenodo	Guidance that can be leveraged by RDA Secretariat and co-chairs. Broader promotion of materials can reach external audiences and support community work in similar institutions based on RDA practices.
5	RDA Knowledge Graph <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annotation tool • Knowledge Base • Deposit Pipeline • Catalogue 	RDA community Software is reusable in other projects and products Commercial end users EOSC Assoc/ Horizon Europe Projects (included in a comprehensive proposal to EUDAT, but no progress yet due to EUDAT commitments in other tasks) Need to identify potential funding sources	DANS	Fee-carrying knowledge management service (similar to ERP deployment: process/strategy consultation followed by data curation and deployment of software-based solution tailored to customers' environment and needs)	Code sustainability: - included into funded projects - Minimum maintenance cost (RDA environment) - Minimum hosting cost Content sustainability: mixture of - RDA TAB - RDA Membership - Funded driver (curator)	RDA to use the Knowledge Graph and KB to enhance findability of outputs and therefore maximise and document the impact of the community's work.

⁸⁷ Papadopoulou, A. (2025). RDA Working Group Facilitation Best Practice Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18012145>

⁸⁸ Papadopoulou, A. (2025). Facilitation Tips & Tools Guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18011922>

KER	Name	Potential users	Lead	KER type	Minimum sustainability	Exploitation paths
6	Landscape analysis of the value of RDA to EOSC / Europe ⁸⁹	Actors within the EOSC ecosystem / EOSC Federation, EOSC Association	RDA Europe	Documentation/ Recommendations	Zenodo	Further alignment with EOSC Federation and through adoption of RDA Group outputs within the EOSC ecosystem, based on identification of relevant outputs provided in the landscape report.
7	Landscape analysis reports and documentation	Funders interested in the RDA community (companies, international organisations or NGOs) wishing to leverage RDA as a neutral platform for developing community recommendations for specific data challenges, broader community	RDA Europe, CODATA and DANS	Fee-carrying Or community enrichment	A platform or model showing initiative connections by topics, disciplines, activities, RPOs & RFOs (cf cordis or EOSC observatory), also using the RDA Knowledge Graph and mappings done as part of the Landscape analysis of the value of RDA to EOSC / Europe.	Documentation and landscape analysis reports created and methodology used for reports, in connection with KER 2.1 can be reused by the broader community (available on Zenodo ⁹⁰ and on the RDA KB ⁹¹), and further expanded with future funding.
8	Selection Committee 'Lessons Learned' info sheet, titled '10 Things for Running a Selection Committee' ⁹²	Other EC-/HE-funded projects running Open Calls/Cascade Grants. (info for this to drawn from content for final WP1 and WP6 project deliverables)	RDA Europe	Documentation	Zenodo; RDA TIGER website page	Project partners and the broader ecosystem can leverage lessons documented during RDA TIGER open call processes to support future endeavours.

6. Conclusion

The RDA TIGER project was the first initiative of its kind within the Research Data Alliance, conceived to provide both in-kind services and targeted financial support to RDA Working Groups (WGs) in order to increase the efficiency of WG operations and to facilitate the uptake and impact of their outputs. To monitor this, the project set out project-wide KPIs as well as service-specific targets that required engaging a relatively large proportion of the RDA's WG community. This need for scale had to be carefully balanced against the project's commitment to enhancing the quality and reach of WG activities, while also ensuring that the services introduced would remain sustainable beyond the project's formal end.

⁸⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18085357>

⁹¹ <https://www.kb-rda.org/>

⁹² O'Connor, R. (2025). 10 Things for Running a Selection Committee (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18033882>

Overall, the project succeeded in striking this balance. RDA TIGER helped numerous newly formed WGs to establish themselves and maintain early momentum, while also providing meaningful support to those WGs who were already established and as they worked toward producing Recommendations and other outputs. As is described in detail in section 4 above, the project was in the main a success when viewed from the perspective of its various key performance indicators and metrics (those with and without targets). Though the precise figures to describe this were not supplied above, RDA TIGER provided support to the majority of active WGs within RDA over the project's lifespan and was at least in part responsible for an uptick in overall activity with respect to the establishment of new WGs and the recruitment of new members into the RDA community over the past three years.

While the dedicated funding period for the project has ended, the RDA TIGER has established sustainability and exploitation pathways, including project-based funding, organisational integration, community uptake, and fee-based or sponsored models. A rich set of openly available documents, tools, and Knowledge Base resources ensures that lessons learned and best practices will continue to benefit the RDA community (and the wider Open Science ecosystem) as a legacy of the project.

In one sense the targets that the project set for itself at the outset and the questions these implied (for example, "Will these services be of interest to the RDA community?", "Will there be sufficient uptake to justify this investment?", "Will the lightweight, distributed structure of RDA WGs align with the more 'centralised' type services provided by RDA TIGER) were answered positively. The feedback mechanisms and the project's own self monitoring and evaluation allowed the project to respond in an agile manner to any suggestions for improvement from supported WGs and the service gaps model described above facilitated the critical self-reflection that was part of the operations of the project's work packages. As well as providing a framework against which to respond to feedback, this service gaps model also underlined the interconnectedness of the project's 'in-kind' service offering and ensured that any responses to feedback were done so at a cross-service or cross-work package level (i.e., not by individual services or work packages). This in turn enhanced both internal project coordination efforts and service users' sense of the overall coherence of the RDA TIGER project or 'brand'.

At the same time, the inherent constraints facing WGs (such as their 18-month lifespan, the voluntary nature of co-chair and member contributions, and the finite level of support RDA TIGER could offer across a large WG portfolio) continued to pose challenges for achieving the level of impact envisioned for each WG. Once WGs conclude, it becomes difficult to gauge how their outputs are adopted in practice and to define what constitutes a "successful" WG in measurable terms. This is partly because RDA outputs are free to access and openly available to anyone with an interest and a relevant challenge to address. They are often cross-disciplinary in scope, and adaptable and adoptable at varying levels, from institutional to regional. It can also take time for WG outputs to be comprehensively adopted and implemented, and are often used in conjunction with other resources as part of the development of technical, policy, process, and operational solutions. All of the above is what

makes the RDA unique; it is also part of the challenge of tracking an output's journey following publication. To this end, the following abridged recommendations are made for other projects or initiatives undertaking a similar assignment:

- Ensure that whatever critical or evaluation framework is employed is one that requires input from multiple participants within and/or across different service providers
- Focus on the concision of key performance indicators, success gauges or metrics, ensuring that each allows you to track something specific (i.e., does not need other information or data to interpret) and worth measuring (i.e., not a “nice to know” statistic)
- Allow space for discussions of service(s) sustainability as early as possible, ideally in parallel to service design and piloting
- Provide multiple methods of feedback to be provided, including ways of recording and responding to conversational and/or anecdotal feedback; communicate to service users the value not only to service providers but to the user community itself of their feedback
- Establish a culture of internal self-evaluation and appraisal of services which allows those delivering the services a say in how these are designed, delivered and adapted.

Addressing the challenges described above and considering these recommendations could be a valuable starting point for any successor initiative to RDA TIGER, helping future projects to shape their targets, refine their service offerings, and ask the right questions from the outset.

Annexes

Annex 1 - RDA TIGER Open Call For Support Services: Selection Committee Evaluation Form

RDA TIGER Support Services Evaluation Form

Thank you for your help in reviewing the applications for the [May 2025 Open Call for RDA TIGER support](#)

** Indicates required question*

1. File identifier of the application you are evaluating, e.g. F9_02_05_25 *

2. Your name (only for internal purposes - will not be shared with applicants) *

3. I am not a member of this existing or potential working group, and cannot identify other potential conflicts of interest with this application *

Mark only one oval.

Agree

Other: _____

Section A.1: Working Group Outputs

On a scale of 1-5, assess to what extent the WG output(s) can contribute to a significant advancement in one or more of the following areas. Please score only the areas that have been filled in. Applicants will not be penalised if they have not filled out more than one area.

4. Creating mechanisms and tools for creation, sharing, management and re-use of research outputs (e.g. data, software, publications, workflows, protocols, and methodologies);

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
No s Very significant advancement

5. Facilitating scientific multidisciplinary cooperation

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
No s Very significant advancement

6. Efficient handling or providing seamless access to large volumes of research outputs

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
No s Very significant advancement

7. Increasing FAIRness, openness and quality of scientific research in Europe and globally

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
No s Very significant advancement

8. Creating meaningful monitoring and research evaluation mechanisms, enabling better reproducibility, validation and re-use of research outputs, or improving pathways for communication of science to the public.

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	
No s <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> Very significant advancement					

9. [Optional] Do you have any additional remarks regarding WG outputs? (300 words maximum)
Please provide constructive feedback, and be aware that this can be passed on to applying groups.

Section A.2: Impact of the Working Group

On a scale of 1-5, candidates are asked to select and expand on one or more of the three areas of impact. Please assess the impact of the application on the area (s) they choose. Do you see a clear strategic impact? Score each area they fill in. Give each area a score of 1-5 and this will be made into an average.

10. Impact area: Supporting the Open Science principles (e.g., [FAIR Principles](#), [CARE Principles](#), [TRUST Principles](#), or as defined in the 'Areas of Action' on p20 of [UNESCO Open Science Recommendations](#)).

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Low High impact

11. Impact area: Strategic goals outlined in the [RDA's current strategic plan](#). Please refer here to the 'Strategic Goals' on p14.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Low High impact

12. Impact area: The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), i.e., the WG is expected to create output(s) that have a clear connection to EOSC. This may include internationalisation or standardisation of existing EOSC outputs and/or creating new outputs that respond to an [EOSC priority](#). Please refer here to the 'Implementation Challenges' on p96 of the SRIA.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Low High impact

13. [Optional] Do you have any additional remarks regarding WG impact? (300 words maximum)

Please provide constructive feedback, and be aware that this can be passed on to applying groups.

Application Type

14. What kind of application are you reviewing?

Mark only one oval.

- Section B: Support Services for the Working Groups provided by the RDA TIGER personnel (also for Material Support applications)
- Section C: Support for hiring external experts for the Working Group (also for External Action applications) *Skip to question 22*

Section B.1: Implementation

The following questions relate to the implementation of the WG. Note that candidates applying for an existing WG only fill in section B.2., while those applying for a new WG fill in both B.1. and B.2.

15. **B.I. Implementation #1:** Explain how the WG will meet its aims and objectives and deliver its outputs. On a scale of 1-5 assess how feasible does this WG plan sound?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not. Very much

16. [Optional] Please provide additional feedback on implementation #1 (300 words maximum). Please be constructive and be aware that this could be used as feedback to the groups.

17. **B.I. Implementation #2:** Detail how the WG will add value to existing work in the RDA and contribute with major European and non-European initiatives and include experts relevant to the output creation. On a scale of 1-5 assess how well this WG fits with the landscape of major European and non-European initiatives

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not. Very much

18. [Optional] Please provide additional feedback on implementation #2 (300 words maximum). Please be constructive and be aware that this could be used as feedback to the groups.

19. **Section B.1:** How would you rate the potential for international connectivity based on the application, i.e. is there potential interest for the WG outside of single region?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

20. **Section B.2. Statement of intent:**

On a scale of 1-5, assess to what extent the applicants have thought about the value of engaging with TIGER?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very much

21. [Optional] Please provide additional feedback on the statement of intent (300 words maximum)

Skip to section 7 (End of review)

Section C: "Support for hiring external experts for the Working Group"

22. On a scale of 1-5, what is the impact that this grant will bring to the WG? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
Very Very high

23. How realistic is the plan in terms of time commitment? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5
Very Very much

24. [Optional] Do you have any additional remarks regarding external expert support? (300 words maximum)
Please provide constructive feedback, and be aware that this can be passed on to applying groups.

End of review

This concludes the review form. Thank you for your assistance in reviewing this application!
Please remember to click 'Submit' below before closing this window

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Annex 2 - RDA new membership before and after the RDA TIGER support started

Support before WGs activity started	Date when support started (YY-MM-DD)	Name of the RDA WGs and link	Number of new RDA membership before support started	Number of new RDA membership after support started	Total of membership	% of new RDA membership
N	2023-01-01	GORC International Model WG	82	14	96	15
N	2023-01-01	National PID Strategies WG	74	9	83	11
N	2023-10-12	RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG	35	12	47	26
N	2023-10-12	RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG	43	9	52	17
N	2023-10-16	EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG	110	33	143	23
N	2023-10-16	RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group	30	11	41	27
N	2024-05-22	Ethics in Agricultural (Ag) Data WG	20	7	27	26
N	2024-06-01	Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG	80	15	95	16
N	2024-06-01	RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software WG (PRO4RS)	72	4	76	5
N	2025-01-28	Global Open Research Commons International Implementations Working Group (GORC II WG)	39	5	44	11
N	2025-09-24	I-ADOPT WG	152	0	152	0
Y	2023-10-17	Harmonised terminologies and	42	18	60	30

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		schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG				
Y	2024-02-02	Wind Energy Community Standards WG	16	10	26	38
Y	2024-02-09	Building Immune Digital Twins WG	21	59	80	74
Y	2024-02-13	Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)	49	14	63	22
Y	2024-03-09	FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG	19	20	39	51
Y	2024-05-09	Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG	23	11	34	32
Y	2024-05-22	Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG	35	11	46	24
Y	2024-06-26	Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG	37	8	45	18
Y	2024-07-29	FAIR Mappings WG	55	20	75	27
Y	2025-01-20	Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG	44	9	53	17
Y	2025-02-11	Common maDMPs API WG	54	16	70	23
Y	2025-08-26	Computational Modelling of Health Data WG	6	0	6	0

Annex 3 - WP2 Communication KPI supplementary materials

The figure shows two screenshots of RDA working group communication pages. The left screenshot is for the 'GORC International Implementations Working Group (GORC II WG)' and the right screenshot is for the 'RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group'. Both pages display a list of posts with columns for 'Subject', 'Replies', and 'Date Modified'. The posts include various meeting notices, reminders, and updates.

Figure 10. Example of internal WG communications in lieu of ‘bulletins’.

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Figure 11. Example WG campaign: RDA TIGER-supported WG Plenary 24 session promotion

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